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Project Website and Logo (Second Release) D6.5

Version 1.1

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The purpose of this deliverable is to offer an update on the work on the Q-SORT project logo and the Q-SORT website, its sections, its technical infrastructures, and its related services.

This deliverable complies with the Q-SORT DoW outlined in Work Package 6, *Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation*. It particularly satisfies specifications outlined in Task 6.1, *Graphic identity study and logo design* and Task 6.3, *Website design and execution*, thus providing a reference point for all necessary actions regarding the promotion of Q-SORT's Web presence.

The promotional elements addressed in the document are the design and definition of the Q-SORT logo, its tagline and its graphic elements (including the website graphics and layout).

It is intended to benefit the work of the following interrelated tasks: Task 6.2, *Dissemination and Engagement planning and execution*; Task 6.4, *Production of materials for Dissemination*.

The current document is comprised of 6 main Chapters, an Executive Summary, Conclusions and an Annex.

The first Chapter describes the Q-SORT branding and visual identity strategies, which notably includes a paragraph devoted to the description of the Q-SORT logo.

Chapters 2, 3, 4, 5 offer respectively a detailed overview of Q-SORT's website layout and structure, its public and reserved areas, its technical infrastructure, the tools it offers, and its interactions with Social Networks and its additional services (e.g., web feeds, analysis tools, etc.).

Chapter 6 describes the workflow of the editorial team and the content of the website's various sections.

NOTE FOR THE RESUBMISSION - V1.1

The first release of the Q-SORT website was conceived and implemented in order to have, online and as quickly as possible, the three 'project essentials', e.g. 1. a strong visual identity to be consistently declined across all the media, 2. all the important information about the project, including contact details, 3. the core website functionalities, such as press area, reserved area, etc. This was done with view to the full version of the website to be released on M8, which would take into account user feedback and incorporate new information in the form of further news, info about the conference and the people behind the project.

This vision reflects modern approaches to communication and outreach, whereby the communication legwork is done chiefly on Social Media (SM), whilst the Project Website works both as the final destination of the traffic generated on SM, and as the ultimate project showcase. As explained in D6.2 and D6.3, as well as during the WP6 Review Meeting Talk, this is the strategy that ensures best value for money for communication, since, thanks to their advanced personalised targeting functionalities, SM maximise the number of users reached and engaged per unit work. The approach adopted by QED for WP6 is also 'modern' in the sense that it is based mainly on pursuing Public Awareness of Science (PAWS) and Public Engagement on Science and Technology (PEST).

Further to the recommendations of the Reviewers (see footnotes no.s 1-5 in D6.3), extra sections devoted to the Public Understanding of Science (PUS) as well as to project-specific information (investigators, publications, etc.) have been added to the Q-SORT website: for their descriptions, see chapter 2.4 in this document. The copywriting throughout the website has also been reviewed and expanded so as to make explanations more informative and easier to understand.

For a concise discussion of modern (PAWS, PEST) vs. traditional (PUS) approaches to science communication, see **Note for the resubmission** in D6.3.

1 THE Q-SORT LOGO

1.1 Q-SORT VISUAL IDENTITY

The study of a visual identity for Q-SORT was challenging since the project inception, due to the specialist nature of the subject matter as well to the difficulty of explaining the basic features of the sorter without making reference to mathematical descriptions.

Because we are convinced that a careful dissemination of the project's results will be of great value not only to academic but also to lay circles, a vigorous push towards engagement with non-specialised audiences has been a guiding principle in our work since the beginning. We feel that a low standard of design and copywriting has in the past been the cause of (otherwise-excellent) science projects' limited success in attracting a general audience. Luckily (also thanks to the efforts of the European Commission), the situation has been evolving quickly in recent years: there is a growing investment in communication, branding and public relations aimed towards a wider audience.

In keeping pace with these positive outreach initiatives, we believe that Q-SORT's branding approach should be driven principally by an emphasis on the following strengths: 1) the beauty and richness of meaning of the concepts and of the imagery that the project entails; 2) the scientific excellence of its endeavour and of the participating institutions.

In accordance with the parameters of our DoW, a professionally-conducted study of Q-SORT's visual identity and branding was undertaken. We are confident that this investment will bring added value to the project and distinctive advantages to the consortium. At the core of our efforts is the intention of developing an overall 'look-and-feel', a unique and easily identifiable personality to be consistently declined across all platforms used during dissemination. This undertaking includes the following branding elements :

1. Basic Elements

- i. *Brand logo*, i.e. the symbol through which the project is easily recognised, in both print and electronic media, and notably in thumbnails pertaining to social media profiles and browser favicons.
- ii. *Branding architecture*, meaning a coherent system of typographical rules, visual relations, and hierarchies between the brand-logo and the (typo)graphical elements connectable to it (e.g. the Q-SORT brand-logo and event titles).
- iii. *Tagline*, an encapsulation of Q-SORT 'brand personality', summarising what Q-SORT is with a short and easy to remember sentence.

2. Web

- i. Templates for the web pages that are compatible with WordPress and the CMS of the website. In particular, these include: a. main website page; b. general page template, e.g. About the project; c. news & events pages template; e. contacts page template, etc.

A vast selection of TEM- and vortex-related images and motifs was assembled for the visual identity study. Graphic artists were also briefed qualitatively on various aspects of the science behind the project and of the challenges involved in the project activities. The first element arising from the visual identity study was the design of the Q-SORT logo.

1.2 THE Q-SORT Logo

The logo has to concurrently fulfil several functions. Namely, it should be: instantly recognisable, elegant, representative of the project, simple, easy to reproduce at various different sizes and on many different media. Ideally, it should also have evocative qualities.

In designing it, it was our intention from the outset to seek to provide a graphic analogue of some of the concepts and/or experimental procedures that are characteristic of the sorter. We explored and evolved several ideas for designs that could represent various forms of azimuthal symmetry, but also the action of sorting and the many meanings behind the word “sort”, which comes from the Latin for “fate”, i.e. *sors*, *sortis*. Interestingly, and poignantly, *sors*, *sortis* also means the response given by an oracle, i.e. the outcome of a divination: gaining an insight and being able to discern are also actions afforded by the sorter. As it is customary at QED, the designs were evolved by selection but also through a form of ‘horizontal gene transfer’, i.e. by sometimes grafting features from one design to another.

Throughout the design phase, we followed QED’s usual guiding principles of clarity and simplicity, which notably entail the adoption of a minimalistic tonal and chromatic palette, as well as checking that the design works first and foremost in monochrome.

Another guiding principle has been the suitability of the design to be animated as part of a possible ident which we are thinking of splicing in at the beginning of the Q-SORT webinars and social media videos (TBC in D6.2 - Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan).

We also had to take into account the use of the logo within the intended website design, together with the associated tagline (see 1.2), and also within the intended designs for other future Q-SORT graphic assets -such as brochures, posters, vinyl banners, possibly a handout gadget, etc.-, which will be specified in D6.2 - Dissemination and Public Engagement Plan. This meant, *inter alia*, clearly differentiating between the project logo and the textures of the website images - for example those arising from complex caustics. Other constraints we had to keep in mind were the reproduction of the logo as a thumbnail in social media and as a favicon in browsers, which imply the elimination or strong aliasing of fine details.

After several generations, we finally settled on the idea of the ‘open’ Q, based on pictures from a research article by Matteucci, Missiroli, Muccini, and Pozzi¹: whereby the stroke of the letter Q represents a charged micro tip cutting across electron equiphase lines (see Figures 3 and 4). In the end, for several practical and aesthetic reasons, but also for greater simplicity, we decided to evolve the logo into a full logotype for the word “Q-SORT” (Figures 1 and 3), rather than keeping logo and project title separate.

¹ Matteucci G, Missiroli GF, Muccini M, Pozzi G, *Electron holography in the study of the electrostatic fields: the case of charged microtips*, *Ultramicroscopy* **45**, 77-83 (1992)

Figure 1. Q-SORT project logo and icons

Figure 2. Study for a possible animation for the Q-SORT logotype

Figure 3. Q-SORT logo colour palette

Figure 4. Q-SORT logo and its constituent elements

*Figure 5. The pictures that inspired the 'cut' in the structure of the letter Q: a charged micro tip cutting across electron equiphase lines; from Matteucci G, Missiroli GF, Muccini M, Pozzi G, Ultramicroscopy **45**, 77-83 (1992)*

Figure 6. How the Q-SORT logo works in conjunction with other project/website artwork

Figure 7. Some of the sketches made by Luca Giberti as part of the study for the Q-SORT project logo

1.3 THE Q-SORT TAGLINE

A central component of the Q-SORT 'brand personality', the tagline summarises what Q-SORT is with a short and easy-to-remember sentence.

The chosen tagline is: *Q-SORT. A New Era in Electron Microscopy.*

These words were chosen carefully so as to highlight the revolutionary nature of the sorter. The mention of the electron microscope ensures the widest possible inclusion in search-engine queries.

1.4 RECEPTION OF THE Q-SORT LOGO AND RELATED WORK AFTER THE RELEASE OF THE FIRST VERSION

The logo was well received and garnered the praise of several partners.

With view to future animation and graphic design work, QED experimented with alternative colour schemes for the logo. The creative director Luca Giberti decided nevertheless to stick with the white-over-black and black-over-white versions.

The logo and its constituent elements, which gradually 'come together' to form it, symbolise the inductive process inherent to empirical science - whereby a conceptual picture gradually emerges based on several observations/measurements. This inspired us to seek to animate the logo. Two animations were therefore developed:

One, for the website landing page, emphasising some of the basic elements which inspired the idea of the sorter, i.e. the electrostatic needle and the vortex (see Figure 24).

The other animation was produced in After Effects and set to a looping music, specifically composed to this end, in order to work as an animated monoscope to be played before and after the live Interdisciplinary Webinars. Playback of a video loop is customary practice in live streaming as it helps to ensure that 'early bird' viewers are not put off by the lack of sound and movement in their video window.

The individual elements of the Q-SORT logo were also used as a leitmotif in the design of the Conference subpages (see 2.3).

2 THE Q-SORT WEBSITE

The following domain has been registered for the project website:

<http://www.qsort.eu/>

The website is the keystone of the project communication and dissemination strategy, as well as a tool for work for the partners.

Figure 8. Logic view of first release of Q-SORT website; downloadable files are represented by rectangles

2.1 FUNCTIONS OF THE PROJECT WEBSITE

The Q-SORT website is the first port of call for anyone wanting to know more about the project. At the same time, it is also the Q-SORT's own visiting card, so to speak.

Other important features of the website are:

- its usefulness for journalists and media people, who can download press kits and photos;
- its operational function as an online repository for all the project documents;
- its blog/news feature, which acts as the very first publishing outlet for news about Q-SORT, which will then be re-posted to social media.

Due to this multitude of needs, the website was conceived and designed inspired by criteria of clarity, functionality, simplicity, and beauty. Everything is intended to drive the user's attention on the main function of the website: to provide information about the Q-SORT project, its activities, progress, and achievements.

Since the Internet has become a mostly mobile medium, the website was conceived from the onset to be smartphone and tablet ready. That is why we adopted a responsive web design solution, i.e. "...a Web design approach aimed at crafting sites to provide an optimal viewing experience – easy reading and navigation with a minimum of resizing, panning, and scrolling - across a wide range of devices (from desktop computer monitors to mobile phones)" (Wikipedia).

The Q-SORT website is W3C compliant.

2.2 STRUCTURE AND LAYOUT

The website structure and the design of its graphical user interface were conceived bearing in mind the main scenarios of use and the resulting 'user trajectories' from the moment users land on the home page until they reach the information they seek. Model readers thus considered include the following three macro categories: users interested in knowing more about the project (including schools), scientists managers and admins working in the project, journalists.

For the latter two groups, the logical layout of the main navigation bar (see below) and the shallow nature of the page tree (Figure 8) result in the fastest possible path from landing on the home page to retrieving the desired information.

On the other hand, users who are just generally curious are invited to dwell on the rich, high-resolution scientific imagery on which the design is based. Images are a key feature of the Q-SORT website and of the Q-SORT communication in general. They are the easiest way to begin communicating and generating interest in complex information, not only amongst professionals but also within the general public.

Black and white was used predominantly for several reasons: primarily, to make the website stand out in the hyper-crowded and multicoloured landscape of the Web; but also, in order to make the few colour elements within it stand out, which is especially useful for highlighting items of great importance - such as the EU flag.

The website structure and content will evolve in time according to the needs of the project and of its partners.

2.2.1 Landing page

The landing (home) page of the website is a clean-looking and intuitive access point from which all further navigation ensues.

It features a large picture background which is representative of Q-SORT. In the lower portion of the landing page is the main navigation bar. At the bottom of the page the user will find the EU flag and the "This project is funded by the EU" caption.

2.2.2 The main navigation bar

The horizontal navigation bar features the following links (NB: the texts for each of the following subpages are given in Annex 1):

Q-SORT

A button for getting back to the home page.

Figure 9. Q-SORT home page

About

A page providing all the important facts about the project, featuring the following paragraphs:

Who we are

A brief description of the Q-SORT Partners, with links to their respective websites.

What we do

A summary of the overall mission and activities past and future of the project, which will be updated as Q-SORT progresses.

Figure 10. Q-SORT About page

Figure 11. Q-SORT About page

Figure 12. Q-SORT About page

Figure 13. Q-SORT About page

Figure 14. Q-SORT About page

EU Funded

A brief introduction to the EC and EC projects, with special emphasis on FET.

Figure 15. Q-SORT EU Funded page

Science

A concise description of the scientific background of the project, providing links to further reading.

News

The news section provides news about the project in a standard, easy-to-read format. It is strongly connected with the social networking environment (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram). This is a critical step towards successful dissemination and community engagement in this technological age. As far as possible, images will be employed to communicate each entry.

This section will feature news and events that are relevant for the Q-SORT community, including diary-like updates about Q-SORT progress, notices of events organised by Q-SORT, of events organised by other institutions, of projects that have invited Q-SORT partners to promote the project's activities, and of other events of interest for the Q-SORT community and target users.

Press

This section features useful material for journalists and media people such as the partners' press offices. The latest Q-SORT press release, project photos, and the Q-SORT logo can be downloaded directly through the following three links:

Download the latest press release

Download press photos

Download the Q-SORT logo

Photos come as an individual zip file, as do various versions of the logo intended for different uses, as per Figure 1.

Further promotional material such as brochures, posters, etc. will be added as the project progresses for download and use by partners in dissemination/outreach events. There will also be an outreach kit that can be used by the project partners as well as by external users in order to produce customised promotional posts.

Contacts

An easy-to-read access point for communicating with the Q-SORT team.

2.2.3 Reserved area

A specific section of the website is reserved for the Q-SORT partners, the EC Project Officer and the reviewers. Access to this section requires the entry of a username/password. The related link is placed at the bottom of the home page, so as to declutter the main navigation bar.

The following sections describe the information and services that are hosted in this private area.

THE Q-SORT REPOSITORY

The Project repository stores all the documentation with restricted circulation, such as:

- lists of deliverables, including peer reviewers and due dates
- Grant Agreement, Description of Work and all the official documents exchanged with the EC to set up and start the project
- final deliverables submitted to the EC

- information related to the Project meetings: project presentations shown during the meetings, agenda, minutes, etc.
- administrative documents (timesheets, periodic reports, etc.)
- document templates such as those prepared for deliverables, presentations, and reporting of dissemination activities
- any other document determined to be useful for the Project partners

The repository is accessed via a user-friendly interface that allows a simple, fast and secure access to large files and documents.

The navigation tree contains one folder per Work Package, each of which is managed autonomously by a WP leader.

Each authorized partner can upload/download/replace files and create directories. Each page of the tree displays the size of the uploaded files as well as the date of their uploading.

Only the administrator is allowed to delete files and manage sharing and permissions settings.

A specific folder will be dedicated to the Review Meetings, which aim to collect relevant documents for PO and reviewers' easy access (it will include documents such as periodic partners' cost claims, deliverables under review, Description of Work, the review agenda and related practical information, review reports and any other relevant material).

THE Q-SORT CALENDAR

The Q-SORT reserved area embeds a Google Calendar to offer an easy access point to important professional events related to the Project. Google Calendar is a free time-management web application that will help the consortium in sharing events of common interest.

All the users authorized to access the reserved area can view the Calendar, but only the WP/Task leaders have permission to create new events.

2.3 RECEPTION OF THE Q-SORT WEBSITE AND FURTHER WORK AFTER FIRST RELEASE

The website was well received by both the Project Partners and the general audience². Expressions of interest for QED's work also came via email as a result.

Partners were encouraged to provide ongoing feedback. As a result, a number of small adjustments was made as a result, albeit without changing the overall website structure. Changes were also made according to new needs arising from ongoing Project activities. In this sense, a project website is never really 'finished', but keeps evolving in order to better satisfy project needs or to accommodate new developments.

The most important changes were the addition of a wholly new section devoted to the first Q-SORT International Conference, a renovated landing page, a People page devoted to key project personnel.

Conference

A specific page and several subpages devoted to the first Q-SORT International Conference were set up. This Conference section was devised so as to be easy to expand, in order to accommodate future Q-SORT conferences. The leitmotif of the Conference subpages was given by the individual elements of the Q-SORT logo, depicted in red. The colour red was introduced for the first time in the otherwise strictly monochrome website, to put emphasis on the upcoming conference, but also to signify a live event - as opposed to purely online content.

Broadly speaking, the Conference section featured two successive layouts, devised in response to the evolving conference needs:

² E.g.: "The website looks amazing. My compliments to those who designed and built it!" Partner FEI Thermo-Fisher"; It looks wonderful! It works particularly well on mobile devices." Partner FZJ

At first, a so-called 'booking' layout was set up, featuring stronger emphasis on how to participate in the conference, how to submit a talk or a poster, how to book travel and accommodation.

Secondly, after enrolment was closed, a 'pre-conference' layout was deployed, with greater emphasis on travel details, practicalities, the up-to-date programme, and so on.

Figure 16. Q-SORT Conference main page

Figure 17. Q-SORT Programme subpage (PDF)

Figure 18. Q-SORT Travel and speaker info subpage

Figure 19. Q-SORT Special events subpage

Figure 20. Q-SORT Invited speakers subpage

Figure 21. Q-SORT Registration subpage

Figure 22. Q-SORT Submission guidelines subpage

Landing page

A red announcement of the upcoming Q-SORT International Conference was added to the landing page, together with a colour photo of Aachen, the closest city to the conference location, where participants would be staying. This first use of colour in the otherwise strictly monochrome website was meant to emphasise the upcoming live event.

Figure 23. Q-SORT International Conference announcement on Landing page

The Q-SORT logo on the very first screen features a new animation that is effected by the scrolling, which highlights the connection between the project logo and its constituent parts (see pictures).

Figure 24. Q-SORT new animated logo on Landing page

People

The People page was set up in order to offer details of the project staff (photos, biographies, recently completed projects). Now it features only the Principal Investigator bio and it will be updated during the next 6 months.

Figure 25. Q-SORT People page

2.4 FURTHER WORK FOLLOWING THE FIRST PROJECT REVIEW

Since the Reviewers recommended featuring more content on the Website devoted to popular explanations (as per Footnotes no.s 1 to 5 in D6.3), we

1. expanded and clarified the copywriting in the various existing sections of the Website, including relevant links to internal or external webpages for further clarifications
2. wrote and included the several new pages, which feature further explanations in laypersons' terms.

A comprehensive description of the new structure and new pages of the Q-SORT website is provided below.

2.5 THIRD RELEASE OF THE Q-SORT WEBSITE

The website now features an updated structure which is illustrated in the diagram below:

Figure 26 - Q-SORT website structure

Science

The Science section of the website has been revisited and now features four sub-pages and namely:

- **A layperson's introduction to the science of Q-SORT**

It presents a short explanation of the project in simple terms with engaging language.

Figure 27. Q-SORT - Science section, sub-page devoted to an introduction to Q-SORT for the layperson.

- **The main concepts behind Q-SORT**

It describes in the most accessible terms the main scientific concepts behind Q-SORT in the form of a glossary featuring links.

Figure 28. Q-SORT - Science section, sub-page devoted to the explanation of the main concepts behind Q-SORT

- **Introductory Bibliography**

An introductory scientific bibliography to published research articles on the science behind Q-SORT.

Figure 29. Q-SORT - Science section, sub-page devoted to an introductory bibliography of the project

- **Access to the Q-SORT open data and publications**

This page is the gateway to the Q-SORT community on [ZENODO](#), the general-purpose [open-access repository](#) developed under the European [OpenAIRE](#) program and operated by [CERN](#).^{[1][2]} It features a comprehensive list of the Q-SORT:

- open data sets
- open access and non-open access research articles
- articles on Q-SORT
- Q-SORT deliverables

Figure 30. Science section, sub-page devoted to the Access to the Q-SORT open data and publications

People

This section has been expanded to include the bios of the other members of the Q-SORT project team.

Figure 31. Update of the "People" page

Webinars

This is a new section of the Q-SORT website.

It features the Interdisciplinary Training Webinars organised by Q-SORT.

Figure 32. Q-SORT - Webinars section, sub-page devoted to one of the interdisciplinary training webinars

Events

This is a new section of the Q-SORT website. It substitutes the old “Conference” section.

It features the past, current and future events organised by Q-SORT such as the Q-SORT International Conferences.

Figure 33. Q-SORT - Events, sub-page devoted to the Q-SORT 2019 International Conference

News

The News page has been updated with a fresh new look and enriched with news regarding the project. It will further enriched during the following months of the project.

Figure 34. Q-SORT - Update of the 'News' page

Press Room and Downloads

The following page was further updated and the following content is available for download:

- The Q-SORT Logos
- The Outreach Toolkit featuring sample press release, social media updates, emails, hashtags images pertaining the Q-SORT Kick-off meeting
- The Outreach Toolkit featuring sample press release, social media updates, emails, hashtags images pertaining the Q-SORT 2018 International conference
- The Q-SORT 2018 Conference Book of Abstract
- The Q-SORT 2018 Conference Poster

Links to the Q-SORT social channels are featured as well as the email address for the Q-SORT mailing-list.

Future plans foresee the inclusion of:

1. Q-SORT 2019 Outreach Toolikit;
2. Images for the press

Figure 35. Q-SORT - Press Room and Downloads Page

3 TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE

The Content Management System that has been selected as the base technology for the Q-SORT website is WordPress³ - is a free, open-source blog tool and publishing platform licensed under the GNU General Public License (GPL). WordPress is powered by PHP and MySQL and can easily be customised into a Content Management System (CMS). It has been selected as the base technology for the implementation of the Q-SORT website because of its flexibility, its user-friendly setup and usage, and its provision of a high level of personalisation. Moreover, its widespread availability has engendered a rich ecosystem of plug-ins, which allow users and developers to extend its functionality beyond the features that come with the base installation. This ensemble of qualities makes WordPress the ideal facilitator of a versatile CMS. Moreover, since it is available for free, it represents maximum value for money.

WordPress has a web template system that uses a template processor. The processor makes it easy to re-arrange widgets and install and switch between themes. The PHP and HTML code used by the themes can also be edited for more advanced customizations.

WordPress has a number of useful features, which include integrated link management, a search-engine-friendly, clean permalink structure; the ability to assign nested, multiple categories for articles; support for tagging of posts and articles. Automatic filters are also included, providing standardised formatting and styling of text within articles.

Multimedia files such as images, videos, flash movies, image galleries, slideshows, etc. can be uploaded and linked to (or displayed in) pages and articles, or embedded directly from other places (e.g. YouTube).

WordPress provides several ready-to-use options for the display of website archives. They can be arranged according to year, month, week, day, category, or author. New archives can be created and easily linked. Since WordPress generates pages dynamically, all these archive pages come at no additional space-cost to the server.

WordPress' built-in search functionality allows visitors to the website to search for terms they are interested in; the search terms are highlighted, making it is even easier for them to find what they were looking for.

WordPress supports the Trackback⁴ and Pingback⁵ standards for displaying links to other sites that have themselves been linked to a post or article.

4 SERVICES AND OTHER WEBPAGES

4.1 SOCIAL NETWORK INTEGRATION

The Q-SORT website allows for easy, one-click sharing, bookmarking, and emailing of articles and pages through the provision of a large variety of services.

In particular, AddThis is the add-on tool intended to make sharing and bookmarking simple, and to place at the immediate disposition of users all of the leading web 2.0 social networking, bookmarking, blogging, and email services⁶. Once added, visitors to the website can bookmark an item using through services such as Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest, LinkedIn, Google+ and many more. Q-SORT Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram pages will be created in order to engage a wider public made up of both professionals and nonprofessionals.

The updating of the Facebook page is done either automatically or manually by the authorised managers; automatic updating is based on feeds taken from the Q-SORT website and the posting of news and select memes of interest to the Q-SORT target audience. Authorised managers can manually post information

³ www.wordpress.org

⁴ http://www.sixapart.com/pronet/docs/trackback_spec

⁵ <http://www.hixie.ch/specs/pingback/pingback>

⁶ The code is available at <http://www.addthis.com/>

about events or other relevant information related to the project or partners, as well as select content proposed by the partners. QED is responsible for managing the social network pages.

4.2 WEBSITE STATISTICS

Website usage is monitored through Google Analytics, a very popular Web analytics solution that provides many insights into one's website traffic and marketing effectiveness. It allows for Advanced Segmentation, Custom Reports, Advanced Analysis Tools, Analytics Intelligence, Custom Variables, and Data exports⁷.

Google Analytics can track visitors from all referrers, including search engines, display advertising, pay-per-click networks, email marketing, and digital 'collateral' such as links within PDF documents.

The service offers the following specific statistical insights:

- number of visits and number of unique visitors
- visit duration and last visits
- domains/countries of visitors
- host list, last visits and unresolved IP addresses list, most viewed, entry and exit pages
- browsers used
- robot visits
- search engines, keyphrases and keywords used to arrive at site

Statistics are managed by the webmaster; they are analysed on a tri-monthly basis in order to verify trends and variations.

4.3 FURTHER WORK ON DATA GATHERING AFTER FIRST WEBSITE RELEASE

In order to gain more insights into user behaviour, two scripts were recently added to the Q-SORT website code:

1. Facebook Pixel was installed in order to provide more insight on user behaviour besides Google Analytics, and better integration with Facebook. This is especially useful given the emphasis we have put so far on Facebook as a tool for outreach.
2. The free version of Hotjar was also installed (www.hotjar.com) in order to better characterise the effectiveness of the graphical user interface (GUI) of the Website.

Insights provided by these two tools will be discussed in future deliverables, so as to allow for sufficiently meaningful amounts of data to accumulate.

5 THE CONTENT

5.1 EDITORIAL TEAM

The **Editorial Team** is comprised of the following members:

- the Communication and Dissemination Manager (Dr. Luca Giberti, QED) and the Project Coordinator (Dr. Vincenzo Grillo, CNR) are in charge of deciding overall strategy and monitoring the activities;
- the Communication and Dissemination Executive (Dr. Raffaella Santucci, QED) is in charge of producing, proofreading, checking, and validating the content and publishing the content on the website.

The content to be published on the website is provided by all partners; contributions can be sent to the editorial team.

⁷ For individual features, see http://www.google.com/intl/en_uk/analytics/features.html

An **Editorial Board** for the website will be established for quality control of the texts of the website through an internal call for participation. Editors in Chief of the Board are Vincenzo Grillo and Luca Giberti. The texts to be published on the website will be first shared and agreed upon between the members of the Board. In the event of dispute, a simple one-vote-per-partner, with majority voting, can be used for decision making. In a tied situation, the Editors in Chief have the casting vote.

Other content posted only on social media, such as individual images or shared links to other online resources, will be emailed *ex post* to the members of the Editorial Board.

5.2 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

The Q-SORT Project is the sole responsible party for content published on the website; it does not represent the opinion of the European Commission.

The text of the Q-SORT web pages is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 (by) license⁸. This means that users are free to share (copy, distribute, and transmit), remix (adapt), and make commercial use of the website's editorial content under the following conditions:

- **Attribution** — Work must be attributed in the manner specified by the author or licensor (but not in any way that suggests that they endorse you or your use of the work)

It must be noted, however, that the rights to images and videos published on the website are dependent upon the respective attributions of each content provider and may not fall under the above CC licence. Each image has a specific caption with all relevant information.

All other specific contents may be licensed differently according to agreements with single authors.

⁸ <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>

6 CONCLUSION

This deliverable describes the work carried out to define the Project's visual identity and to implement the Project's website.

It has to be noted that the current release of this deliverable presents the first stage in the development of the website. The website will be continuously and timely updated along the project's lifetime, and its structure may change to take into account new requirements.

For the duration of the Project's life, the editorial team will continue to:

- constantly update the content of the website
- publish news and events in a timely fashion
- make project deliverables and other documentation available in a timely fashion.

ANNEX 1: LIST OF THE PAGES IN THE THIRD RELEASE OF THE Q-SORT WEBSITE

Q-SORT [=landing page]

About

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A layperson's introduction to Q-SORT research (New!)
The main concepts behind Q-SORT (New!)
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Press & Downloads (Updated!)

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Download the Book of Abstracts

Download the Q-SORT Poster

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ABOUT THE PROJECT

Who we are

The Q-SORT Consortium comprises some of the top players in the world of orbital angular momentum (OAM), quantum optics, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) including cryoTEM:

CNR-NANO (Project Coordinator) - Italy
Forschungszentrum Jülich - Germany
FEI (Thermo Fisher Scientific) - The Netherlands
Max Planck Institut - Germany
University of Glasgow - United Kingdom
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - United Kingdom
Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia - Italy
Maastricht University - The Netherlands

The Consortium has been tailor-made in order to reach project goals as quickly and effectively as possible, but also to attain maximum impact in the scientific world and in society at large. The wide cross-section of skills and geographical spread in the Consortium ensure that all requirements of *responsiveness and adaptive change, diversity and inclusion, openness and transparency, anticipation and reflection* are satisfied.

Members of the Consortium complement each other thus: CNR, Forschungszentrum Jülich, and University of Modena and Reggio Emilia are world leaders in electron-beam shaping; University of Glasgow and Max Planck Institute are pioneers in OAM and quantum optics; Maastricht University is an important innovator in protein studies; Thermo Fisher (formerly FEI) is a major world-wide developer and manufacturer of microscopes; QED is a young SME from the creative industry led by an award-winning producer-director.

What we do

Q-SORT introduces a revolutionary concept whereby the transmission electron microscope (TEM) is employed as a so-called **Quantum Sorter**, i.e. a device that is able to pick out and display detailed information about electron quantum states. This in turn provides researchers with precious new information about the sample being examined.

The project -which includes applications in physics, biology, and biochemistry- is expected to have a wide-ranging impact due to the ubiquitous adoption of TEM and STEM across many disciplines. Indeed, strong interdisciplinarity, featuring a multi-year collaboration between physicists and biologists, is one of Q-SORT's defining traits. The project features a strong international consortium with potential industrial applications.

Q-SORT also has foundational value in physics as it fosters its own kind of sparse-sensing approach to TEM, advancing the field in the direction of quantum measurement. Intuitively, sparse sensing is analogous to how we recognise familiar people from just a few small details: it means that only a few measurements are taken compared to traditional approaches - yet these are still sufficient to extract all the relevant information. A similar thing happens when we recognise relatives just from their silhouette or profile or any other small detail: we don't need to see their full face to identify them.

The scientific coordinator and principal investigator of Q-SORT is **Vincenzo Grillo**, a senior research fellow at CNR -the Italian National Research Council- and the recipient of the prestigious Humboldt Foundation's Bessel Research Award for his work on beam shaping.

The project also features an international advisory board led by Ebrahim Karimi (University of Ottawa), who has a long-standing collaboration with the principal investigator, Vincenzo Grillo.

A policy based on equal opportunities and gender balance informs the entire project.

Science (Updated!)

A layperson's introduction to Q-SORT research (New!)

The Q-SORT project is working on developing a new generation of electron microscopes – so-called “Quantum Sorters”, able to probe delicate specimens with extremely low sample damage. The potential benefits of such tools include, but are not limited to, the ability to determine protein structures that could lead to new drug designs for healthcare and next-generation biomedicine.

For decades scientists, art-science buffs, and the wider public have marvelled at the beautiful worlds revealed by electron microscopy, from the hideous beauty of an insect's mouthparts to the shimmering world of meta-materials at the molecular level. Modern machines can now fire powerful electron beams to produce images with single-atom resolution.

But electron microscopes are much more than simple imagers. Probing properties such as the composition of a sample or its magnetic, mechanic, structural, or electronic properties, their flexibility as tools of investigation has made them precious allies for testing fundamental physics.

Electron microscopy is thus fundamental to unveil the smallest secrets of the natural world. (For an easy introduction to electron microscopy, see for example <https://www.fei.com/introduction-to-electron-microscopy/history/> and the following pages.)

One important issue in modern electron microscopy is that electron beams can damage samples as they strike them. This so-called “dose problem” is particularly serious when the sample is very delicate, like a protein for example. When imaging samples, the dose problem forces scientists to seek an awkward trade-off between resolution and sample integrity. Careful specimen handling is key in important research fields, such as biology and biochemistry, that typically feature delicate samples, due to their organic chemical make-up.

Q-SORT aims to develop radically new techniques to explore and study fragile specimens at the microscopic level, uncovering an array of information that was previously hidden.

Q-SORT exploits TEM (transmission electron microscopy), a technique in which a beam of electrons is passed through an ultra-thin slice of specimen to form an image on a CCD camera.

Unlike previous incarnations of this technology, Q-SORT takes advantage of recently-developed techniques that allow scientists to shape electron beams according to their needs: electron beams can be structured either by means of nanofabricated electron holograms or via electrostatic (or magnetostatic) lenses. These novel devices can also split the beam in its component quantum states, thus turning the TEM into what project scientists call a “quantum state sorter” or “quantum sorter”. These sorters can probe

the properties of samples with very few electrons, allowing scientists to answer tricky questions about the specimens with maximum efficiency and extremely low damage.

The advantage of the sorter, compared to 'traditional' forms of TEM, stems from the idea of re-thinking the set-up of the electron microscope in order to optimise the extraction from the sample of a specific quantity of interest. This is achieved through the operation of sorting specific electron quantum states out of the electron beam, after it has interacted with the sample. Knowledge of this decomposition provides useful and often unique information about the sample.

Q-SORT's primary goal is to develop and validate tools and techniques enabling researchers to perform quantum sorting. The Project is also pursuing their application to a selected number of systems of interest.

The successful marriage of the Sorter to cryomicroscopy is especially exciting. Cryomicroscopy is a technique generally used for biological specimens, in which a flash-frozen solution is fed into a TEM. In cryomicroscopy the techniques developed by Q-SORT can be used to recognise protein structures, symmetries, and orientations. These proteins can be cell-signalling molecules, or parts of membranes, which ultimately provide researchers with knowledge of how cells and tissues function. The new information gathered from quantum sorting could eventually be applicable in drug design for healthcare and next-generation biomedicine. Progress in the development of cryomicroscopy led to the Nobel Prize for Chemistry in 2017. Application of the Sorter to cryoTEM is one of the four objectives of Q-SORT.

Moreover, the Sorter is a multipurpose tool which will be useful in many other fields besides biochemistry. This new paradigm in measurement should allow researchers to map magnetism down to the atomic scale. It should also afford the investigation of various types of exotic electronic excitations (e.g. plasmons) in materials. Probing magnetic spin properties and the physics of plasmons is part of the four-fold goal of Q-SORT.

Besides the above three examples, the concept of a quantum sorter that extracts hidden information with maximum efficiency is of potential use in a variety of other applications and systems.

The main concepts behind Q-SORT (New!)

The following is a list of significant words that recur in the Q-SORT webpages, as well as in the research articles where Q-SORT results are published. Follow the links within the text to delve deeper in each concept.

Electron

The [electron](#) is an elementary particle normally bound to an atom. Scientists can easily obtain free electrons from [a variety of sources](#) that work by wrenching electrons away from atoms, exploiting different physical mechanisms. Depending on the situation, electrons can [behave as waves or as particles](#). This is one of the puzzling aspects of quantum mechanics.

An electron is described by a quantum mechanical [wavefunction](#), which in general stretches all over the three-dimensional space. The wavefunction is obtained as a solution of the [Schroedinger equation](#) or, if the electron is moving at extremely high speed, of the [Dirac equation](#).

Electron microscope

Invented by [Ernst Ruska](#) and [Max Knoll](#) in 1933, the electron microscope uses electrons instead of photons in order to probe the sample.

Amongst other things, this allows researchers to achieve much greater resolutions and magnifications compared to optical microscopes.

This is due to the fact that scientists can decrease the wavelength of electrons at will by accelerating them with suitable electric fields. This in turn increases the [resolving power](#) of the microscope, which is directly proportional to the wavelength of the probing particle.

The same cannot be done with photons, as their wavelength in a given medium is determined once they are emitted by the source, and stays fixed until they are absorbed. Moreover, photons in the visible

spectrum have a lower limit for their wavelength, which is significantly greater than the wavelengths typically attainable by an electron microscope.

Electrons fired onto the sample interact with it in a variety of ways: they can bounce off losing energy, they can traverse it and be delayed, and so on. Electron microscopes come in various forms according to the way they employ electrons and pick up the signals resulting from their interaction with matter. If the microscope picks up the electron beam as transmitted through the sample, one has TEM ([transmission electron microscopy](#)). TEM can achieve the highest resolutions, allowing scientists to image even individual atoms, but is limited to thin samples. If the transmitted beam is raster scanned across the sample, one has STEM ([scanning transmission electron microscopy](#)). If the electron beam is raster scanned across the sample and the resulting loss of energy is picked up point by point, one has SEM ([scanning electron microscopy](#)). Many other [probing strategies making use of electrons](#) are possible.

Coherence

In physics two waves are said to be coherent if they have exactly the same frequency and a constant phase difference. For example, white light is incoherent as it consists of different frequencies. In an electron microscope only one electron at a time is flying through, so the coherence is defined between two parts of the same electron wavefunction.

Perfect coherence does not exist in the real world, as actual wave packets have a finite size that typically depends on the emission process. So it is customary to talk about a coherence length, that is defined by the [cross-correlation](#) (or [auto-correlation](#)) function of the wave with another wave (or with itself). Depending on whether the correlation is calculated along the propagation direction or its orthogonal plane, we speak of longitudinal (or temporal) coherence and of spatial coherence respectively.

The degree of coherence is a very important factor in all experiments concerning Q-SORT .

OAM

Short for orbital angular momentum. Intuitively, this gives a measure of how fast a particle is orbiting around a certain axis. Whilst in classical physics the OAM can take any value, in quantum mechanics -which provides the correct description of TEM physics- only certain OAM values are allowed, i.e. OAM is quantised.

In TEM, the OAM of an electron beam transmitted through a sample provides information on the rotational symmetries of the sample. Amongst other things, the Sorter (see below) allows researchers to analyse the various OAM components of an electron beam.

Vortex beam

Quantum mechanics allows scientists to shape a beam of photons or of electrons in the form of a vortex. This is an impossible feat according to classical physics, since in classical physics particles such as electrons travel only in straight lines in the absence of fields bending their trajectories. On the other hand, thanks to the [uncertainty principle](#), quantum mechanics allows an electron to follow many classical trajectories at the same time: the vortex is born out of this superposition of skewed trajectories.

More specifically, in the case of vortex beams the straight classical trajectories are arranged so as to form a [hyperboloid of one sheet](#). This [ruled surface](#) is commonly seen when one cooks spaghetti:

The above figure shows the helical wavefronts of vortex beams and the corresponding envelope of classical straight trajectories, the same one that a twisted sheaf of spaghetti tends to form. The vortex is helical as the wavefront has to be perpendicular to the direction of propagation of the wave. This is a consequence of the Schroedinger equation.

Just like in atomic orbitals no electron can be said to actually orbit around the nucleus -orbitals are just a convenient name for a probability cloud-, so in vortex beams no electron can be said to actually orbit around an axis. In other words, the helical wavefront of the vortex beam describes just the spatial distribution of probability of finding the electron – the electron itself is somewhat delocalised.

Bessel beam

Vortex beams, like all wavefunctions, are solutions of the Schroedinger equation. Solving the latter in cylindrical coordinates yields a family of functions known as Bessel beams. Each Bessel beam in the family is characterised by two numbers, one of which is integer and corresponds to a quantised value of the OAM. The amplitude of Bessel beams on the plane perpendicular to the propagation direction is always the same, irrespective of the propagation distance.

Laguerre-Gauss beam

Laguerre-Gauss beams are also a family of solutions of the Schroedinger equation. They are obtained by solving it in cylindrical coordinates under the paraxial approximation. Each L-G beam in the family is characterised by two integer numbers, one of which corresponds to a quantised value of the OAM. L-G beams expand on the plane perpendicular to the propagation direction, as the propagation distance increases. Unlike Bessel beams, L-G beams can be physically realised.

Quantum Sorter

The wavefunction of the electron can be thought of as a sum of components, just as white light is actually comprised of light of many different colours.

Just like a prism can split white light into its colour components, the Sorter can split the electron wavefunction so as to visualise its different components in different positions on a screen or a detector.

Mathematically, the Sorter effects a unitary transformation of the electron wavefunction. The unitarity of the transformation guarantees that no information carried by the wavefunction is lost.

Hologram

Holograms were first demonstrated by [Gabor](#) using photons. The Quantum Sorter employs special nanofabricated holograms that work on electrons: they are used in order to shape the electron beam so that it possesses certain desired properties.

Holography comes from the Greek words ὅλος (hólos; “whole”) and γραφή (graphḗ; “writing” or “drawing”). Holography as invented by Gabor can be viewed as a special form of photography that preserves the phase information that is normally lost in the process of imaging (hence the holo- prefix): by recording a specially-devised interference pattern on a photosensitive surface, Gabor was able to store the information on the phase of the photons as they interacted with the object that was being imaged. Passing light through the hologram allowed Gabor to recreate the same photon wavefront, even when the object was absent.

The holograms employed by the Quantum Sorter are not physically recorded like those of Gabor but are fabricated using a FIB ([focused ion beam](#)), as the result of electron-interference simulations done on a computer. This is why they are called synthetic holograms.

Kinoform

In the scientific literature this term is generally used for holograms that modulate just the phase of the wavefunction but not its amplitude.

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Access to Q-SORT open data and publications (New!)

In December 2013, the European Commission announced their commitment to open data through the Pilot on Open Research Data, as part of the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme.

The Pilot's aim is to "improve and maximise access to and re-use of research data generated by projects for the benefit of society and the economy". Results of publicly-funded research should thus be made more easily accessible, for the benefit of researchers, innovative industry, and citizens.

Q-SORT is taking part in the Pilot on Open Research Data. To this end, the Q-SORT Consortium chose to make use of **ZENODO**, a free general-purpose [open-access repository](#) developed under the European [OpenAIRE](#) program and operated by [CERN](#).

ZENODO allows researchers to upload data sets, research software, reports, and any other research-related digital artefact. For each submission, a persistent [Digital Object Identifier\(DOI\)](#) is minted, which makes the stored items easily citable.

Q-SORT stores on ZENODO the following types of data:

- open data sets
- open access and non-open access research articles
- articles on Q-SORT
- Q-SORT deliverables.

A comprehensive list of the uploaded Q-SORT files is available for download from the [Q-SORT Community on ZENODO](#).

The data collected by the Q-SORT Community is periodically curated and uploaded in collaboration with the OpenAire Team.

People (Updated!)

Vincenzo Grillo is the Scientific Coordinator and Principal Investigator of the Q-SORT Project. He graduated in physics from the University of Genova (110/110 cum laude). He received his PhD in electron microscopy at the University of Parma, while performing collaborative work with Erlangen university (Germany). In 2001 he was a visiting scientist at the Tokyo Institute of Technology working on cathodoluminescence in TEM. Since 2003 he has been working in the INFM (now absorbed by CNR) as a Senior Fellow researcher in electron microscopy. He has developed innovative TEM-STEM methodology and published the first quantitative use of STEM with HAADF detector for chemical analyses. He is now working on Vortex beams and holographic beam generation. He and his group are now among the world's leading groups in this sector for their work on phase holograms, large vortex beams and the theory of spin-orbit coupling with vortex. In 2015 he was a visiting researcher at the University of Oregon. In 2016 he received the Humboldt Foundation's BESSEL research award for his work on Beam shaping. Dr. Grillo is co-author of at least 100 articles and 5 book chapters. The H-factor of his publications is 32.

The Q-SORT Team

National Research Council (Italy)

Gian Carlo Gazzadi received his PhD in Physics from the University of Modena in 1997. He is a Senior Technologist at the CNR-NANO-S3 center in Modena where he is the coordinator of the nanofabrication facility. His primary research interest are the nanofabrication with Dual Beam focused ion beam (FIB) – scanning electron microscope (SEM) systems. FIB activity includes: nanofabrication of holographic plates and samples for electron interference experiments, nanopatterning of surfaces for nanomagnetism and nanotribology studies, fabrication of nanogap electrodes, nanomachining of scanning probe tips. Regarding electron-beam nanofabrication, the main interest is about focused electron beam-induced deposition (FEBID) of nanostructures from gas precursors, and their characterization from a structural and electrical viewpoint. He has 88 publications on international journals (ISI h-index 17), 3 book chapters, 1 national patent. He is a steering committee member of the focused electron beam-induced processing (FEBIP) international workshop.

Alberto Roncaglia received a M. Sc. degree in Electrical Engineering and a Ph. D. degree in Electronics and Computer Science in 1998 and 2002, respectively, both from Bologna University. In 2001 he joined the Institute of Microelectronics and Microsystems (IMM) of the Italian National Research Council (CNR) as a scientific researcher. His research interests include design, simulation and technology development for the fabrication of micro- and nano-electro-mechanical systems (MEMS and NEMS).

Forschungszentrum Juelich GmbH (Germany)

Rafal Dunin-Borkowski is Director of the Institute for Microstructure Research and the Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons in Forschungszentrum Jülich and Professor of Experimental Physics in RWTH Aachen University in Germany. Between 2007 and 2010, he was Director of the Center for Electron Nanoscopy in the Technical University of Denmark. From 2000 to 2006, he held a Royal Society University Research Fellowship in the University of Cambridge. He has also held postdoctoral appointments in Oxford University, Arizona State University and the University of Cambridge. He obtained his first degree (physics, 1990) and PhD (materials science, 1994) from the University of Cambridge. He specializes in the characterization of magnetic and electronic materials at the highest spatial resolution using advanced transmission electron microscopy techniques, including aberration-corrected high-resolution transmission electron microscopy, quantitative image analysis in electron microscopy, electron tomography and off-axis electron holography. He has published more than 250 journal papers and book chapters and given more than 230 invited lectures and seminars. In 2009, he was awarded the Ernst Ruska Prize of the German Society for Electron Microscopy. In 2012, he was awarded an Advanced Grant by the European Research Council. His H-factor is 41 on ISI WEB and 47 on GScholar.

Amir Hossein Tavabi is a scientific staff member in the Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons in Forschungszentrum Jülich, focusing on advanced transmission electron microscopy and spectroscopy of new materials, *in situ* working devices and novel electron wavefronts. He obtained his first degree in materials science in 2005 and completed his PhD (in electrical engineering and computer science) in Nagoya University, Japan in 2012. In 2012, he worked in the EcoTopia Science Institute in Nagoya. He joined the Ernst Ruska-Centre in 2013 as a postdoctoral research scientist.

Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light (Germany)

Gerd Leuchs is Full professor of physics at the Institute of Optics, Information and Photonics of the University Erlangen-Nuremberg. Since 2009 scientific member of the Max Planck Society and director at the Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light. Member of the Germany national Academy of Sciences Leopoldina, German Physical Society, European Physical Society, German Society of Applied Optics, Optical Society of America, Institute of Physics (London), and the American Association for the Advancement of Science. More than 200 publications in scientific journals and editor of 3 books. 2005 he

obtained the Quantum Electronics and Optics Prize of the European Physical Society. Since 2013 he is visiting professor at University of Ottawa.

Ebrahim Karimi received his BSc in Physics with emphasis in mathematics from Kerman University. He joined the mathematical physics group in IASBS for the graduate study and was ranked 18th among all incoming students in Iran. His MSc research focused on “Laser Cooling and Trapping of Natural Atoms”, and got graduated in 2002 under the supervision of Prof Arashmid Nahal and Prof Yousuf Sobouti. During his MSc degree, he also worked on Singular Optics. In 2009, he received PhD degree from the University of Naples “Federico II”, under the supervision of Prof. Lorenzo Marrucci and Prof. Enrico Santamato. He won the best PhD thesis award for his thesis titled “Light orbital angular momentum and its application on the classical and quantum information”. After the PhD, he worked as a postdoctoral fellow under Phorbitech FET project (led by Prof. Lorenzo Marrucci), and in Prof. Robert Boyd’s Quantum Optics group. Prof Ebrahim Karimi is currently holding the Canada Research Chair in the field of Structured Light, and is the group leader of Structural Quantum Optics (SQO) at the University of Ottawa. He is also an adjunct professor at IASBS, and is an Associate Editor of Optics Express (Optical Society of America). Applications of structured quantum waves (light and particles) in modern science are the main subject of his research team.

University of Glasgow (United Kingdom)

Miles Padgett is the Kelvin Chair of Natural Philosophy at the University of Glasgow and is a Royal Society/Wolfson Merit Award holder. In 2001 he was elected to Fellowship of the Royal Society of Edinburgh, of the OSA in 2011, of SPIE in 2012 and in 2014 a Fellow of the Royal Society – the UK’s National Academy. In 2008 Padgett won the Institute of Physics Optics and Photonics Prize, in 2009 the Institute’s Young Medal and in 2014 the Kelvin Medal of the Royal Society of Edinburgh. He is internationally recognised for his leadership in the field of optics and in particular of optical momentum. His best known contributions include an optical spanner for spinning micron-sized objects, use of orbital angular momentum to increase the data capacity of communication systems and an angular form of the Einstein-Podolsky-Rosen (EPR) quantum paradox.

University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (Italy)

Elisa Molinari is Full Professor of Condensed Matter Physics at University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, and coordinator of CNR-NANO-Modena. She is the Director of ‘MaX – Materials at the exascale’, the European Center of Excellence for HPC applications (www.max-centre.eu). Her main research interests are in computational nanoscience and ab-initio quantum theory of materials, including organics of relevance for the present project. In these fields, she has published over 250 papers in international journals and coordinated many EU and national projects (h-index=45 isi). Elisa Molinari is part of national and international ‘women in science’ networks. She has been Associate Secretary General of IUPAP, the International Union for Pure and Applied Physics, and in such capacity she has promoted/joined the main ‘women in science’ initiatives worldwide.

Stefano Frabboni 2005-now: Associate Professor of General Physics, University of Modena e Reggio Emilia. 2003- now: Scientific Director of the Nanofabrication facility -S3 Research Center, Modena (of INFN-CNR, then NANO-CNR since 2010). 2008-10: Director, Ph.D Course in Physics-University of Modena and Reggio Emilia. 2003- Commissioning and start-up of Nanofabrication facility of the S3 Research Center. 1990- Commissioning and start-up of the Transmission electron microscopy laboratory for material science of the University of Modena. His present research interests are in transmission electron microscopy and nanofabrication methodologies. Author of over 130 papers (134 quoted Isi WEB) in international journals; h-index (ISI-Web): 23.

Maastricht University (The Netherlands)

Peter Peters has a long record of past achievements. Since his PhD in 1991 from Utrecht University, his research activities have led him to be recognized as one of the leading scientists in subcellular trafficking within the immune system using electron microscopy. He has made major discoveries about the subcellular trafficking of proteins and mycobacteria. Peters has participated in several prominent collaborations: one with Nobel laureate Stanley Prusiner to study the subcellular site of prion conversion, and another with Hans Clevers in his groundbreaking research on the Wnt pathway. More recently, he has proven himself to be a leader in specimen preparation for cryo-electron tomography and the development of bionanoscience. In addition to his research activities, Peters has held pivotal leadership roles. He has been a Principal Investigator and Professor since 1998. He initiated the establishment of the Netherlands Centre for Electron Nanoscopy (NeCEN, €18M project) that opened in October 2011 and is now part of the EU roadmap of large research infrastructure. He currently holds a Limburg distinguished professorship and codirects the Maastricht Multimodal Molecular Imaging Institute at Maastricht University. His research has been funded by EU, Dutch, and US institutions, totaling over €6M. Peters has published over 110 scientific papers and delivered over 250 invited lectures. Additionally, he holds two patents for his work. His H index is 57. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y5wvMPtYhSg>

Raimond Ravelli is a structural biologist specialised in X-ray crystallography and electron microscopy. After his study (chemistry, cum laude, 1992) and PhD (1998), he moved to the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (Grenoble outstation) where he became team leader as well as principal beamline scientist on world's first third-generation multiple wavelength anomalous dispersion beamline ID14-4 at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility. Catalysed by a NWO personal career grant (Vidi, 2007), he moved back to the Netherlands as assistant professor in electron microscopy. In 2014, he started at the Maastricht University to help set up the new Institute of Nanoscopy. He employs physics, chemistry, engineering and informatics to study biological structures at the highest possible resolution and develops new methods for structure determination. He determined a wide variety of macromolecular structures and complexes, including proteins involved in neurotransmission, cytoskeletal components, viral infection, and protein secretion. He developed both hard- and software to streamline the process of automated data collection and processing on both X-ray crystallography beamlines as well as the electron microscope. His large-scale electron microscopic images have been displayed at the museum Boijmans van Beuningen in Rotterdam (temporary exhibition Science and Art) and Naturalis Biodiversity Museum in Leiden (permanent exhibition), and have been included in the Guinness World Records book as largest digital recording (2013). He (co-)authored almost 100 peer-reviewed scientific papers (cited ~7100 times, H index of 43). He is scientific referee of numerous journals, member of numerous national and international advisory committees, chairman of the Dutch crystallography association, and (co-)organizer of numerous national and international meetings and workshops.

FEI Electron Optics BV – Thermofisher (The Netherlands)

Frank de Jong is world-wide Director of Research and Advanced Technology for FEI Company; a US-based company selling Tools for Nanotech, focusing on Electron Microscopy and Focused Ion-beam equipment. The European part of the company is based in Eindhoven, The Netherlands, and is a major centre for R&D. De Jong started his professional career at the Philips Research Laboratory in 1984. He graduated in Applied Physics at Delft University in 1990. In 1992 he started working for the Philips Electron Optics business group; which later merged with FEI Company. He became Director for Research and Technology in 2006; since 2011 acting in a global role.

Peter Tiemeijer studied experimental and theoretical physics at the University of Utrecht (NL). His PhD thesis was on numerical analysis of the relativistic dynamics of quarks in mesons. In 1994, he joined Philips Research (Eindhoven, NL) and later FEI Company (Eindhoven, NL) to work on the design and development of electron-optical instrumentation such as a monochromator for STEM, a chromatic aberration corrector for SEM, the optics of the Titan microscope, and the high-brightness field emission gun. Presently he is staff scientist at FEI. He has about 14 US patents and 25 scientific papers

QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd.

Luca Giberti is an award-winning director, producer, and cinematographer. After graduating in Physics at Genoa University and at Oxford University, he apprenticed under Abbas Kiarostami and Marco Bellocchio. His theatre shows have been performed worldwide – from the Piccolo in Milan to the Edinburgh Fringe, from the Oxford Playhouse to the Teatro Stabile in Genoa. Amongst these are the national premières for Italy of the science plays “QED” by Peter Parnell and “Breaking the code” by Hugh Whitemore, about Feynman and Turing respectively, both of which were translated by him. He has won prizes as a director, as a cinematographer, as a video artist, as a screenwriter, including accolades from the Italian Academy of Arts in Rome (Accademia Nazionale di San Luca) and from several film festivals (Berlinale Talents, Venice Biennale Cinema, et al.). For two years he was also full-time producer-director for the Italian Council for the Physics of Matter (INFM), responsible for the media output in its entirety – comprising short documentaries and promos for the public understanding of science. He has lectured on directing at Sapienza, University of Rome and at Middlebury College (VT, USA).

Raffaella Santucci is a communication specialist with experience in inter- and intra-institutional communications, media and PR, international relations, public affairs, event planning and management, as well as social media and Web content management. She provides high-quality communication services, helping to reach your target audiences, whether local or global, whether comprising specialists or the general public. A strategic thinker with sophisticated leadership skills. Committed and passionate, driven to achieve high standards. She acts or has acted as a consultant for several institutions, including Sapienza – University of Rome, Coventry University, the Auditorium in Rome (Musica per Roma), Sapienza Innovazione, Promoter Srl, Codice Idee per la Cultura, Wikimedia Italia and QED F&S Productions.

FUNDED BY THE EU

Q-SORT is supported and funded by the FET OPEN Programme of the European Commission.

The European Commission is the executive body of the European Union. Its tasks include implementing decisions and managing the day-to-day business of the EU (en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_Commission), as well as the implementation of the EU budget. As part of its remit, the EC directly funds trans-national scientific research projects through dedicated calls for entries, such as those of the FET Programme.

We would like to thank the European Union for making our project (along with similar projects) possible. We recognise their important function in promoting the advancement of knowledge and in helping to establish fruitful international long-term relationships involving institutions and companies. We believe that these efforts help us all to better understand and appreciate our cultural diversity.

WEBINARS (NEW!)

Cryomicroscopy for macromolecular structure determination

The first Interdisciplinary Training Webinar covers the following topics:

- dose problem in electron microscopy
- cryomicroscopy sample preparation
- protein structure determination in microbiology
- cryomicroscopy imaging
- computer-assisted structural reconstruction
- phase plate use in cryomicroscopy.

The webinar provides other scientists with an introduction to the techniques and applications of cryomicroscopy to the study of biological systems. Cryomicroscopy is done in a specially modified transmission electron microscope, which allows the quick transfer of specially frozen samples into the microscope column, and their subsequent imaging.

The talk explains the use of Volta phase plates, which allow one to convert the phase variation that the sample imparts to the electron beam into an amplitude variation, which is directly observable as an image. The webinar also illustrates the equipment and techniques that are used in order to prepare and then flash-freeze the liquid solution containing the molecules that are to be studied in the cryo electron microscope. It is important that the solution ends up as vitrified ice, as the amorphous structure of such glass-like ice greatly aids the imaging of the molecules.

The talk also highlights molecules and systems of interest, as well as problems that could be addressed by improving physical techniques.

The chief aim of this webinar is to function as primer on cryoTEM. It also aims to initiate the transfer of knowledge from biochemists specialised in cryomicroscopy to the physicists community of Q-SORT, as well as to the physics community at large.

About the speaker

Raimond Ravelli is a structural biologist specialised in X-ray crystallography and electron microscopy. After his study (chemistry, cum laude, 1992) and PhD (1998), he moved to the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (Grenoble outstation) where he became team leader as well as principal beamline scientist on world's first third-generation multiple wavelength anomalous dispersion beamline ID14-4 at the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility. Catalysed by a NWO personal career grant (Vidi, 2007), he moved back to the Netherlands as assistant professor in electron microscopy. In 2014, he started at the Maastricht University to help set up the new Institute of Nanoscopy. He employs physics, chemistry, engineering and informatics to study biological structures at the highest possible resolution and develops new methods for structure determination. He determined a wide variety of macromolecular structures and complexes, including proteins involved in neurotransmission, cytoskeletal components, viral infection, and protein secretion. He developed both hard- and software to streamline the process of automated data collection and processing on both X-ray crystallography beamlines as well as the electron microscope. His large-scale electron microscopic images have been displayed at the museum Boijmans van Beuningen in Rotterdam (temporary exhibition Science and Art) and Naturalis Biodiversity Museum in Leiden (permanent exhibition), and have been included in the Guinness World Records book as largest digital recording (2013). He (co-)authored almost 100 peer-reviewed scientific papers (cited ~7100 times, H index of 43). He is scientific referee of numerous journals, member of numerous national and international advisory committees, chairman of the Dutch crystallography association, and (co-)organizer of numerous national and international meetings and workshops.

Low-damage multi-pass electron microscopy / Mark Kasevich, Stanford University (USA)

The second Q-SORT Interdisciplinary Training Webinar touches upon the following topics:

- low-dose imaging in electron microscopy
- multi-pass TEM
- live-cell electron microscopy
- phase-contrast electron microscopy
- quantum coherence
- entanglement of electrons
- quantum electron microscopy
- quantum Zeno effect

- dark-field microscopy
- ptychography.

One of the most important issues in electron microscopy is the so-called “dose problem”, that is to say the fact that many samples of interest, such as biological systems, are so sensitive to the number of electrons hitting them that they are easily destroyed or damaged. The idea of multi-pass electron microscopy is to increase the signal-to-noise ratio of the microscope not by sending more electrons through the sample but instead by making few electrons pass through the sample more than once. This allows one to increase the phase signal, which is the main effect that objects such as proteins have on the electron wavefunction: in other words, many biological systems of interest have little effect on the amplitude of the electron wavefunction but impart on it a significant phase – the multi-pass approach allows one to improve this phase signal.

The webinar illustrates one of the approaches being pursued in order to achieve multi-pass electron microscopy. It delves into the technicalities involved in its implementation and summarises the recent efforts in this field by the group of Prof. Kasevich at Stanford, which at present (June 2018) is the only one in the world to have built such a machine.

The talk also touches upon other topics related to the idea of a quantum electron microscope. The latter is an even more revolutionary concept, which, thanks to the peculiarities of quantum mechanics, allows for interaction-free measurements. Due to the nature of its working principle, such measurements, however, are limited to the silhouette of the sample under observation.

The webinar is aimed at:

- spreading awareness amongst physicists of the new possibilities afforded by multi-pass techniques
- exchanging ideas between scientists for furthering joint research
- promoting dialogue between the physics and biology/biochemistry communities, establishing a common language between the two disciplines.

About the speaker

Mark Kasevich is a Professor of Physics and Applied Physics at Stanford University. He received his B.A. degree (1985) in Physics from Dartmouth College, a B.A. (1987) in Physics and Philosophy from Oxford University as a Rhodes Scholar, and his Ph.D. (1992) in Applied Physics from Stanford University. He joined the Stanford Physics Department faculty in 1992. From 1997-2002 he was a member of the Yale

Physics Department faculty. He returned to Stanford in 2002. His current research interests are centered on the development of quantum sensors of rotation and acceleration based on cold atoms, application of these sensors to tests of gravitation and quantum mechanics, investigation of many-body quantum effects in cold atomic vapors, and investigation of quantum-enhanced imaging methods. He co-founded AOSense, Inc. (2004) and serves as the company's Consulting Chief Scientist

Programmable phase plates for electrons / Johan Verbeeck, University of Antwerp (Belgium)

The Q-SORT third Interdisciplinary Training Webinar touches upon the following topics:

- spatial light modulators
- coherent phased arrays
- vortex waves / vortex beams
- electrostatic and magnetostatic electron lenses
- programmable electron phase plates
- quantum coherence
- MEMS
- ptychography.

In light optics, spatial light modulators currently allow full control over the wavefront of optical waves, which has led to many new applications, ranging from astrophysics to advanced light microscopy. Analogous devices for electron optics are being developed, with the ultimate aim of attaining the flexibility of spatial light modulators. The idea here is to be able to shape the electron beam by means of a programmable device, before it interacts with the sample. Yet this endeavour is affected by significant constraints, due to the difficulty of exerting extended coherent control over the phase of the electron probe. In the webinar a new idea is illustrated, which seeks to overcome some of the above limitations. The talk also illustrates the potential advantages of this new approach, which include a relatively inexpensive way to correct spherical aberration. The latter is a defect inherent in all microscopes, which is due to the fact that real-world lenses do not follow the exact profile that is needed in order to achieve perfect focusing. (It can in fact be proven -thanks to Schertzer's theorem- that for a system with cylindrical symmetry, such as a microscope, it is impossible to achieve lensing that is free from spherical aberration.)

The webinar is aimed at

- spreading awareness amongst physicists of the new possibilities afforded by spatial light modulators
- exchanging ideas between scientists for furthering joint research
- promoting dialogue between the physics and biology/biochemistry communities, establishing a common language between the two disciplines.

About the speaker

Johan Verbeeck received his PhD degree (2002) from the University of Antwerp. Currently he is a full Professor at the electron microscopy group (EMAT) of the University of Antwerp. Johan Verbeeck is an expert in the field of electron microscopy and electron energy loss spectroscopy focusing both on applications in state of the art materials science as well as on developing new techniques. He is the author of more than 200 ISI contributions and his work has been cited more than 3000 times. In 2011, he received the prestigious Ernst Ruska award for electron microscopy for his contribution to the quantification of EELS spectra and the development of electron vortex beams. He is the author of the EELSMODEL software providing model based quantification to users worldwide. In 2012 he received an ERC starting grant in order to explore the properties of electron vortex waves.

EVENTS (NEW!)

Q-SORT International Conference 2019

2019 Conference / Overview

Q-SORT 2019 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON QUANTUM IMAGING AND ELECTRON BEAM SHAPING

Recent developments in the spatial and temporal shaping of electron beams are on the verge of technological commercialisation, where they would provide routes towards image-resolution enhancement and novel microscopy techniques. Most of these methods, such as passive and dynamic wavepacket modulation, as well as structured light-matter interaction, are inspired by their optical counterpart and have now been explored in transmission electron microscopy. However, other schemes exist, inspired by quantum optics, such as so-called “interaction-free” methods, optimal quantum state tomography, and computational ghost imaging, which may be implemented in electron microscopy. All these new methods hold the promise of improving the imaging of dose-sensitive specimens.

The Q-SORT International Conference on Quantum Imaging and Electron Beam Shaping aims to gather experts from the fields of electron and laser beam shaping, free-space electron optics, and related sub-fields of quantum mechanics. Participants will present and share their latest discoveries and innovations. This meeting will be one of the first of its kind: it is thus uniquely positioned, since luminaries and pioneers from all the above research fields will be present. They will have the possibility to closely interact and exchange ideas for new, interdisciplinary collaborations.

Q-SORT International Conference 2018

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CONFERENCE / OVERVIEW

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON ELECTRON BEAM SHAPING IN SPACE AND TIME

SUNDAY 27 — WEDNESDAY 30

MAY 2018

FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM JÜLICH, GERMANY

This conference is organized jointly by the partners of the projects

Quantum Sorter – A new Measurement Paradigm in Electron Microscopy (H2020-FETOPEN)

Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms (Deutsch-Israelische Projektkooperation grant).

With the support of Forschungszentrum Jülich.

This conference aims to address challenges and opportunities in electron beam shaping and its applications. It will showcase cutting-edge theoretical and experimental developments in the form of invited plenary talks and contributed presentations and include space for product displays. There will be opportunities for networking and discussion, as well as an edit-a-thon, an interdisciplinary workshop and a webinar. Topics sought for the program include (but are not limited to):

Coherent manipulation of electron wavefunctions by light interaction and matter, possibly inspired by recent progress in light (quantum) optics, to produce functional electron waveforms.

Studies of the foundational aspects of quantum physics and their applications to materials science.

Ideas and methods for near-interaction-free and dose-effective imaging of matter.

This conference is hosted by the Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons, which is a joint facility of Forschungszentrum Jülich and RWTH Aachen University.

Organisers:

Ady Arie, Tel Aviv University (Israel)

Rafal E. Dunin-Borkowski, Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany)

Vincenzo Grillo, CNR- NANO (Italy)

Download the pdf of the programme

CONFERENCE PROGRAMME

Sunday 27 May

PGI, Building 04.8, 1st Floor, Room 142-143 Forschungszentrum Jülich Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse 52428
Jülich

Welcome

Pre-Conference Wikipedia Edit-a-Thon

Monday 28 May

Zentralbibliothek

(Building 04.7) Forschungszentrum Jülich Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse 52428 Jülich

Registration

Welcome and Institutional Delegates

Session A. Low Dose Methods

Chair: Rafal Dunin-Borkowski, Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany)

A1 Low-dose cryo electron ptychography via non-convex Bayesian optimization Philipp Pelz, Max Planck Institute (Germany)

A2 Production of arbitrary phase apertures for electron ptychography beams Wouter Van den Broek, Humboldt University of Berlin (Germany)

A3 Next generation sample preparation for fully automated cryo-EM analysis of macromolecular structures and cells

Peter Peters, Maastricht University (The Netherlands)

Remote demonstration from the microscope

Coffee Break

Session B. EMCD, Plasmons and Quantum Phenomena

Chair: Stefano Frabboni, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (Italy)

B1 Measuring the phase and transverse fields of plasmonic excitations Giulio Guzzinati, University of Antwerp (Belgium)

B2 Atomic scale imaging of magnetic circular dichroism by achromatic spatially-resolved electron energy-loss magnetic chiral dichroism

Xiaoyan Zhong, Tsinghua University (PRC)

B3 Theoretical study of the interaction between phase-shaped electrons and surface plasmon modes Hugo Lourenço-Martins, University of Paris-Sud (France)

B4 Investigating the proximity of magnetic dichroic signal by atomic sized electron vortex and aberrated beam.

Devendra Negi, Uppsala University (Sweden)

B5 The cubic phase in quantum mechanics and hydrodynamics Matthias Zimmermann, Ulm University (Germany)

B6 The Cubic Phases of Wave packets in Linear Potential

Georgi Gary Rozenman, Tel Aviv University (Israel) Lunch Break

Invited Speaker - Q-SORT Webinar

Chair: Wolfgang Schleich, Ulm University (Germany)

Low-damage multi-pass electron microscopy

Mark Kasevich, Stanford University (USA)

Session C. QEM and quantum phenomena

Chair: Wolfgang Schleich, Ulm University (Germany)

C1 Optical multi-pass microscopy

Thomas Juffmann, University of Vienna (Austria)

C2 A 10keV Multi-Pass Electron Microscope

Stewart Koppell, Stanford University (USA)

C3 Aberration-Corrected Quantum Electron Microscopy

Marco Turchetti, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (USA)

C4 Simulated Quantum Electron Microscope Images

Yuri Van Staaden, Delft University of Technology (The Netherlands)

C5 A design for combining multi-pass and OAM sorter for dose effective magnetic measurements

Vincenzo Grillo, National Research Council (Italy)

Coffee Break

Round Table: Quantum concepts in electron microscopy
Chair: Vincenzo Grillo, National Research Council (Italy)

Special Seminar: Wolfgang Schleich, Ulm University (Germany)

Social Dinner

Steakhaus El Toro, Große Rurstraße 34, 52428 Jülich

Tuesday 29 May

Zentralbibliothek

(Building 04.7) Forschungszentrum Jülich Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse 52428 Jülich

Registration

Session D. UTEM-Time shaping

Chair: Avraham Gover, Tel Aviv University (Israel)

D1 Ultrafast Transmission Electron Microscopy with High-Coherence Electron Pulses
Tyler Harvey, University of Göttingen (Germany)

D2 meV Resolution in Laser-Assisted Energy-Filtered Transmission Electron Microscopy
Enrico Pomarico, École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (Switzerland)

D3 Temporal manipulation of sub-relativistic electron beams using light and matter
Roy Shiloh, Friedrich-Alexander University (Germany)

D4 Attosecond coherent control of a free-electron wave-function via semi-infinite light fields and plasmon polaritons

Giovanni Maria Vanacore, École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (Switzerland)

D5 The ultrafast and ultracold electron source

Jim Franssen, Eindhoven University (The Netherlands)

Coffee Break

Session E. Light-electron interaction

Chair: Ido Kaminer, Technion – Israel Institute of Technology (Israel)

E1 History-Dependent Radiative Interaction of Single Electron Quantum Wavepacket Avraham Gover, Tel Aviv University (Israel)

E2 Tailoring the Spectral and Angular Response of Smith-Purcell Radiation Roei Remez, Tel Aviv University (Israel)

E3 Spontaneous and Stimulated Radiative emission

of modulated free-electron quantum wavepackets - QED Analysis Yiming Pan, Tel Aviv University (Israel)

E4 Electron-light interaction in Wigner phase space Peter Kling, Ulm University (Germany)

Lunch Break

Q-SORT Science Bash Schlosskapelle

Gymnasium Zitadelle

In der Zitadelle, 52428 Jülich

Speaker: Peter Peters

Title: Beauty and benefits of nanobiology

Session F. Phase plates and beam shaping Chair: Ady Arie, Tel Aviv University (Israel)

F1 Experimental realization of a cylindrical quantum basis set for bandwidth-limited two dimensional electron wavefronts Jun Yuan, University of York (United Kingdom)

F2 Analysis of non-diffractive electron Bessel beams for potential application in electron microscopy

Simon Hettler, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Germany)

F3 Refractive wavefront shaping with a sculpted thin film enables aberration-corrected imaging on uncorrected electron microscopes

Peng-Han Lu, Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany)

F4 Diffractive Guiding Using Slits

Moritz Carmesin, Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (Germany)

F5 Generation of non-diffracting Bessel beams with amorphous carbon phase masks

Lukas Grünwald, Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (Germany)

Invited Speaker - Q-SORT Webinar Chair: Ady Arie, Tel Aviv University (Israel)

Shaping electron wavepackets with light; Shaping light with electron wavepackets

Ido Kaminer, Technion – Israel Institute of Technology (Israel) Coffee Break

Session P. Poster and Exhibitors

Social Dinner

Im Alten Zollhaus, Friedlandstraße 22, 52064 Aachen

Tuesday 29 May

Poster session

Zentralbibliothek

(Building 04.7) Forschungszentrum Jülich Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse 52428 Jülich

P1 Holography in Scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy

Harvey, T.R.; Ophus, C.; Yasin, F.S.; Chess, J.J.; Pierce, J.S.; McMorran, B.J.

P2 Maximizing contrast in cryo-transmission electron microscopy with physical phase plates Obermair, M.; Hettler, S.; Hsieh, C.; Marko, M., Gerthsen, D.

P3 The ultimate direct-electron detector and neural network

van Schayck P.; van Genderen E.; Boulanger E.M.H.; Roussel L., Peters P.; Ravelli R.

P4 Realization of the Feynman-Young thought experiment:

Controlled electron interference in Fraunhofer and image space

Tavabi A.H.; Boothroyd C.B.; Yücelen E.; Frabboni S.; Gazzadi G.C.; Dunin-Borkowski R.E.; Pozzi G.

P5 MEMS fabrication processes for Tunable Amperometric Phase Plate devices Balboni, R.; Roncaglia, A.

P6 Fabrication of an e-beam OAM sorter via Electron Beam Lithography

Rosi, P.; Medici, G.; Menozzi, C.; Venturi F.; Gazzadi, G.C.; Frabboni S.; Grillo, V.

P7 A Numerical Analysis of Interaction-Free Measurement for Low-Dose Imaging Using Conditional Sample Re-illumination

Agarwal, A.; Goyal, V.; Berggren, K. K.

Wednesday 30 May

Zentralbibliothek

(Building 04.7) Forschungszentrum Jülich Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse 52428 Jülich

Registration

Session H. Programmable phase plates and beam shaping

Chair: Johan Verbeeck, University of Antwerp (Belgium)

H1 Nanoelectromechanical systems on a Si-on-insulator chip to act on the phase of the electron wave-field inside a transmission electron microscope

Martial Duchamp, Nanyang Technological University (Singapore)

H2 Recent developments in the design and implementation of phase plates for electrons Marco Beleggia, Technical University of Denmark (Denmark)

H3 Dynamic generation of electron vortices to probe magnetic information in a (S)TEM Armand Béché, University of Antwerp (Belgium)

H4 Electron Mode Conversion and Vortex Generation Christian Kramberger, TU Wien (Austria)

H5 Electrostatic Aharonov-Bohm effect: a tunable electron vortex beam generator Amir H. Tavabi, Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany)

H6 A setup for electron wave front manipulation using patterned electrostatic mirrors Maurice Krielaart, Delft University of Technology (The Netherlands)

H7 Imaging through a multimode fibre using modal correction and time of flight to give 3D images Daan Stellinga, University of Glasgow (United Kingdom)

Coffee Break

Invited Speaker - Q-SORT Webinar

Chair: Ido Kaminer, Technion – Israel Institute of Technology (Israel)

Programmable phase plates for electrons

Johan Verbeeck, University of Antwerp (Belgium)

Concluding Remarks

Lunch

TRAVEL INFO

Q-SORT-DIP 2018 - TRAVEL INFO

Hashtag: #QSORTDIP2018

Follow us on FB: www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/

Local Contacts

Penghan Lu, p.lu@fz-juelich.de, +49 159 0535 6660.

Marie Göcking, m.goecking@fz-juelich.de

Event Locations

May 27, 2018: Pre-conference Wikipedia Edit-a-thon

PGI, Building 04.8, 1st Floor, Room 142-143

Forschungszentrum Jülich

Leo-Brandt-Straße, 52428 Jülich

May 28-30, 2018:

Zentralbibliothek (Building 04.7)

Forschungszentrum Jülich

Leo-Brandt-Straße, 52428 Jülich

Where to stay

For the convenience of all, Forschungszentrum Jülich has been kind enough to book a block of rooms at the following hotel:

Hampton by Hilton Aachen Tivoli

Merowinger Strasse 2, 52070, Aachen, Germany

TEL: +49-241-9559300 FAX: +49-241-955930955

Discounted prices are as follows:

79 Eur for a single room

89 Eur for a double room

In order to obtain this discounted rate please inform the hotel that you are attending the “Q-SORT Workshop” when you book.

Rooms are still available at the Hampton, we strongly suggest that you book your room there as soon as possible.

Bus Transportation

Forschungszentrum Jülich kindly organized a bus transfer to pick up the conference attendees. In the morning, the pickups will take place at the following address/time:

Pick up point 1:

Hampton by Hilton Aachen Tivoli

Merowinger Strasse 2, 52070, Aachen, Germany

TEL: +49-241-9559300 FAX: +49-241-955930955

Time:

- Sunday at 2:00 PM

- Monday- Wed at 8:00 AM

A bus will also bring people every evening from Forschungszentrum Jülich back to Aachen (Hampton Hotel and Bus Station) and to the restaurants and back.

Special Events

May 27, 2018: Pre-conference Wikipedia Edit-a-thon

PGI, Building 04.8, 1st Floor, Room 142-143

Forschungszentrum Jülich - Leo-Brandt-Straße, 52428 Jülich

An Edit-a-thon is an initiative in which people (in our case scientists!) gather to edit/create/improve Wikipedia pages on a given topic.

It is meant for anybody who uses Wikipedia and we invite PhD students and researchers to participate!

It is a great occasion to learn how Wikipedia works and get together.

Participation is welcome but obviously not mandatory!

The goal of this event is to edit and update descriptions in Wikipedia of concepts such as electron vortex beams, two slit experiments with electrons and synthetic holography, where information gaps currently exist. This event is organized with the support of Wikimedia Italia.

More info for those interested in participating and not sure what an Edit-a-thon is are available here: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Edit-a-thon>

Social dinners

28 May 2018, h. 19:00 - Steakhaus EL Toro

Große Rurstraße 34, 52428 Jülich

phone: 02461 58100

29 May 2018, h. 19:00 - Im alten Zollhaus

Friedlandstraße 22, 52064 Aachen

phone: 0241 404050

Meeting registration

<http://www.qsort.eu/conference-registration/>

How to get there

By Car

Coming from Cologne (Köln) take the A 4 motorway (Cologne – Aachen), leave the motorway at the Düren exit, and then turn right towards Jülich (B 56). After about 10 km, turn off to the right onto the L 253, and follow the signs for “Forschungszentrum”.

Coming from Aachen take the A 44 motorway (Aachen – Düsseldorf) and leave the motorway at the Jülich-West exit. At the first roundabout turn left towards Jülich, and at the second roundabout turn right towards Düren (B 56). After about 5 km, turn left onto the L 253 and follow the signs to “Forschungszentrum”.

Coming from Düsseldorf Airport take the A 52 motorway (towards Düsseldorf/Mönchengladbach), followed by the A 57 (towards Cologne). Turn off at Neuss-West, and continue on the A 46 until you reach the crossroads “Kreuz Wanlo”. Take the A 61 (towards Koblenz/Aachen) until you reach “Dreieck Jackerath” where you should take the A 44 (towards Aachen). Continue as described in “Coming from Düsseldorf”.

Coming from Düsseldorf on the A44 motorway (Düsseldorf – Aachen) you have two options:

1. (Shorter route but more traffic) turn right at the Jülich-Ost exit onto the B 55n, which you should follow for approx. 500 m before turning right towards Jülich. After 200m turn left and continue until you reach the “Merscher Höhe” roundabout. Turn left here, drive past the Solar Campus belonging to the University of Applied Sciences and continue straight along Brunnenstrasse. Cross the Römerstrasse junction, continue straight ahead onto Wiesenstrasse and then after the roundabout and the caravan dealers, turn left towards “Forschungszentrum” (signposted).

2. (Longer but quicker route) drive until you reach the “Jülich-West” exit. At the first roundabout turn left towards Jülich, and at the second roundabout turn right towards Düren (B 56). After about 5 km, turn left onto the L 253 and follow the signs to “Forschungszentrum”.

Navigation systems

In your navigation system, enter your destination as “Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse”. From there, it is only a few hundred metres to the main entrance – simply follow the signs. The research centre itself is not part of the network of public roads and is therefore not recognised by navigation systems.

From neighbouring airports by train:

From Cologne Bonn Airport

From the railway station at the airport, please take the overground line S 12 (“S-Bahn”) to Düren. Continue from Düren as described in “By train”.

From Düsseldorf International Airport

From the railway station at the airport, travel to Cologne main train station and then continue on to Düren. Some trains go directly to Düren whereas other connections involve a change at Cologne main train station.

Continue from Düren as described in “By train”.

By train:

Take the train from Aachen or Cologne to the train station in Düren. From here, take the local train (“Rurtalbahn” [RTB]) for Jülich and get out at the “Forschungszentrum” stop. To make sure that the train stops at “Forschungszentrum” you should press the request stop button (Haltewunsch) in good time after the “Selgersdorf” stop.

From the train stop, a shuttle service will bring you to the campus (for all trains arriving between 6 am and 7 pm, for the timetables, please see “Aachen – Jülich bus connections” below).

If you walk, it will take you approximately 20 minutes to reach the main entrance. The distance is about 1.3 kilometres.

→ time tables for trains from Düren to Jülich (please choose “RB 21” in the field “Linie” to get the train time tables to Jülich. The name of the route is Düren – Linnich)

→ time table for SB 219 shuttle service (between Rurtalbahn stop and Forschungszentrum Jülich) (PDF, 25 kB)

Aachen – Jülich bus connection:

The SB 20 and the 220 bus lines connect Forschungszentrum Jülich to the local public transport system.

time tables:

→ Bus SB 20 Aachen – Forschungszentrum Jülich (PDF, 25 kB)

→ Bus 220 Aachen – Mariadorf – Aldenhoven – Jülich – FZ Jülich (PDF, 61 kB)

AVV website with timetables for bus routes (please chose “SB 20” or “220” in the field “Linie” to get the time tables of the buses to Jülich)

Map:

Download map (PDF)

Local Map:

Download map (PDF)

SPEAKER INFO

Q-SORT-DIP 2018 - SPEAKER INFORMATION

This page contains information and resources to assist you as a presenter at the Q-SORT- DIP 2018 Conference.

If you do not find an answer to your question, please contact us.

Hashtag: #QSORTDIP2018

Follow us on FB: www.facebook.com/quantumsorter/

General Speaker Information

Do I need to register to present?

As a speaker, you must register to present. Be sure to register here:

<http://www.qsort.eu/conference-registration/>

Papers

The oral presentations at the conference will be 15 minutes long.

Posters

All accepted posters will displayed during the whole duration of the conference.

Is there a PowerPoint template I should use for my presentation?

We prepared an optional template for your convenience. (NOTE: If using a personal PowerPoint template, it would be helpful if you could use Arial font to avoid conversion issues).

How can I share my presentation materials, and should I include a copyright statement?

We invite you share your presentation by sending your file(s) or URLs before the conference (and no later than May 21, 2018) to:

quantumsorter@gmail.com

We ask that you fill in your PowerPoint document's properties in the following manner prior to sending us the file.

Title: TITLE

Subject:QSORT-DIP 2018

Author: NAME(S)

If you password-protect a PDF document, please make sure to enable the file to be read by a screen reader.

It is our goal to make our resources easily available.

You may use this copyright statement on one of your first slides:

“This presentation leaves copyright of the content to the presenter. Unless otherwise noted in the materials, uploaded content carries the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike license, which grants usage to the general public with the stipulated criteria.”

How will my room be set up?

The room will have theater-style seating. There will be a head table and chairs for speakers at the front of the room.

Will I have access to audio/video equipment?

All of the session rooms (with the exception of poster sessions) will have the following standard AV:

- Projector
- Screen
- Microphones

Will I have Internet access?

The following internet connections will be available:

- Wireless access will be available for everyone, presenters and attendees. The connection speed will be sufficient to access and navigate web pages and e-mail.

What will the area for my poster look like?

The standard set should include a bulletin board. Push pins, scissors, tape and other supplies will be available at the check-in desk.

When can I set up and take down my poster display?

Set up times:

- May 27, 2018 3:30 p.m. onwards.

The recommended size of each poster is 120 cm x 90 cm (height x width).

Display boards are 145 cm x 120 cm (height x width).

The suggested structure for each poster is:

Summary

Introduction

Materials and methods

Results/discussion/conclusions (literature cited)

A staff member will be at the front of the poster area and help to direct you to your pre-assigned space.

Do I have the option to ship or store my materials?

If you need to ship materials, it would be best to send them to your hotel (labeled to your attention).

HOTELS AND ACCOMODATION

For the convenience of all, Forschungszentrum Jülich has been kind enough to book a block of rooms at the following hotel:

Hampton by Hilton Aachen Tivoli

Merowinger Strasse 2, 52070, Aachen, Germany

TEL: +49-241-9559300 FAX: +49-241-955930955

Discounted prices are as follows:

79 Eur for a single room

89 Eur for a double room

Rooms are reserved until 23 April 2018.

In order to obtain this discounted rate please inform the hotel that you are attending the “Q-SORT Workshop” when you book.

SPECIAL EVENTS

Wikipedia Edit-a-thon

Duration: 3 hours

Location: PGI, Building 04.8, 1st Floor, Room 142-143

Forschungszentrum Jülich

Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse

52428 Jülich

Time: Sunday 27 May, h15:00

The goal of this event is to edit and/or update Wikipedia articles on concepts such as electron vortex beams, the double-slit experiment with electrons, synthetic holography, etc. where information gaps currently exist. This event is organized with the support of Wikimedia Deutschland and Wikimedia Italia.

Interdisciplinary Webinars

Duration: 1 hour each

Location: Zentralbibliothek, Building 04.7

Forschungszentrum Jülich

Wilhelm-Johnen-Strasse

52428 Jülich

Times:

Monday 28 May, h13:45

Tuesday 29 May, h14:45

Wednesday 30 May, h11:00

These are part of a series of interdisciplinary webinars aimed at promoting dialogue between the physics and biology/biochemistry communities. They will provide an opportunity for mutual learning mentored by senior scientists, in order to exchange ideas for furthering joint research and establishing a common language.

Science Bash

Schönheit und Nutzen der Nanobiologie

(Beauty and benefits of nanobiology)

A user friendly conference with Q&A

by Prof. Peter Peters (Maastricht University)

Duration: 1 hour

Location: Schlosskapelle

Gymnasium Zitadelle

In der Zitadelle

52428 Jülich

Time: 29 May 2018, h13:15

Abstracts:

Download (PDF)

About

Prof. Peter Peters was instrumental in improving cryo-immunogold EM and vitreous cryo-sectioning. His team discovered that mycobacteria causing tuberculosis move from the phagosome into the cytosol (one of the top 10 cited articles in tuberculosis in the last 10 years). He initiated the Netherlands Centre for Electron Nanoscopy (NeCEN). He co-directs the Maastricht Multimodal Molecular Imaging Institute, in which native unfixed cells are studied with 3D cryo-electron tomography in order to visualise molecular machines in the context of cellular organelles. His group aims to resolve the type VII secretion system of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* within the phagolysosome. He initiated a new start-up CryoSol-World, that will produce the next generation vitrification devices called Vitrojet. Vitrobots developed in Maastricht have been distributed to more than 500 cryo-EM labs worldwide. His research has been reported in 120 articles with more than 25000 citations.

www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/m4i

INVITED SPEAKERS

Johan Verbeeck received his PhD degree (2002) from the University of Antwerp. Currently he is a full Professor at the electron microscopy group (EMAT) of the University of Antwerp. Johan Verbeeck is an expert in the field of electron microscopy and electron energy loss spectroscopy focusing both on applications in state of the art materials science as well as on developing new techniques. He is the author of more than 200 ISI contributions and his work has been cited more than 3000 times. In 2011, he received the prestigious Ernst Ruska award for electron microscopy for his contribution to the quantification of EELS spectra and the development of electron vortex beams. He is the author of the EELSMODEL software providing model based quantification to users worldwide. In 2012 he received an ERC starting grant in order to explore the properties of electron vortex waves.

Ido Kaminer is a faculty member at the Technion Faculty of Electrical Engineering. He studies the fundamentals of light-matter interactions in nanophotonics and in settings of 2D materials, developing new concepts for light generation in spectral ranges inaccessible by existing technology. Ido's research specifically focuses on the light-matter interactions of shaped particle wavefunctions, in which he made contributions to the quantum electrodynamics of relativistic electron wavefunctions. Ido is an Azrieli Faculty Fellow and won a Rothschild Fellowship, MIT-Technion Scholarship, and a Marie Curie Fellowship, for his postdoc. During his PhD, Ido has discovered new classes of accelerating beams in nonlinear optics and electromagnetism, for which he received the 2012 Israel Physical Society Prize, and the 2014 APS Award for Outstanding Doctoral Dissertation in Laser Science.

Mark Kasevich is a Professor of Physics and Applied Physics at Stanford University. He received his B.A. degree (1985) in Physics from Dartmouth College, a B.A. (1987) in Physics and Philosophy from Oxford University as a Rhodes Scholar, and his Ph.D. (1992) in Applied Physics from Stanford University. He joined the Stanford Physics Department faculty in 1992. From 1997-2002 he was a member of the Yale Physics Department faculty. He returned to Stanford in 2002. His current research interests are centered on the development of quantum sensors of rotation and acceleration based on cold atoms, application of these sensors to tests of gravitation and quantum mechanics, investigation of many-body quantum effects in cold atomic vapors, and investigation of quantum-enhanced imaging methods. He co-founded AOSense, Inc. (2004) and serves as the company's Consulting Chief Scientist

PROGRAMME COMMITTEE

Programme Chairs:

Ady Arie, Technion (IL)

Rafal Dunin-Borkowski, Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany)

Vincenzo Grillo, CNR-NANO (Italy)

Contact Point:

Vincenzo Grillo, CNR-NANO (Italy)

Conference production:

Raffaella Santucci, QED

Local administrative support:

Marie Göcking, Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany)

General Administrative Support:

CNR-NANO (Italy)

REGISTRATION

The conference will be free of charge, but places are limited.

Coffee breaks and lunches will be provided.

Participants will be responsible for their own travel and hotel costs.

Please register and indicate your hotel preferences before May 21, 2018.

Abstract submission form

Registration form

SUBMISSION GUIDELINES

Extended abstracts should be submitted online here.

Templates are available here:

docx Kit

LaTeX Kit

Contributions will be reviewed and selected by the scientific programme committee. They will have a CC-BY-NC-ND licence with open access, available shortly after the conference.

The committee will decide whether accepted submissions will be presented as talks or posters.

Important dates:

* Submission of 1-3 page extended abstracts: 28 February 2018 / 14 March 2018

* Response to authors: 16 March 2018 / 28 March 2018

* Camera ready versions: 16 April 2018

NEWS (UPDATE!)

This section is designed to collect news and inspire conversations about Q-SORT-related events both inside and outside of the project's immediate sphere.

If you come across an article, blog post, or other piece discussing the Q-SORT project (or if you write one yourself), we would love for you to share it with us: raffaella@qedproductions.co.uk

Here you will also find a list of upcoming talks, tours, conferences, lectures, and meetings related to the Q-SORT project. Q-SORT events create networking opportunities for scientists, scholars, authors, publishers, educators, representatives from public and private science organisations and the general public. Such connections are crucial to the vision of our project and the work we do as promoters of science. We cordially invite you to join in our stimulating discussions.

Chocks off for Q-SORT!

[KoM photo]

The Q-SORT partners at the Kick-off Meeting in Modena, Italy

On **2 October 2017** the **CNR-NANO** institute in Modena hosted the **Q-SORT Kick-off Meeting** for the official launch and first-ever public presentation of the Q-SORT Project. Funded by the European Commission under its highly competitive **Future and Emerging Technologies** Programme (FET), the project will run for 42 months, starting on 1 October 2017.

The Kick-off event - which was organised by Q-SORT and supported by CNR-NANO- brought together leading institutions in the field of electron microscopy and quantum light optics, i.e. CNR-NANO (Project scientific coordinator), the Forschungszentrum Jülich, Thermo Fisher Scientific, The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light, University of Glasgow, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Maastricht University, University of Ottawa.

Representatives from the European Commission, Wikimedia, and the creative industries were also in attendance.

At a glance:

Q-SORT
A New Era in Electron Microscopy

Kick-off Meeting

Dates: 02-03 October 2017
Venue: Palazzo dei Musei
Viale Vittorio Veneto 5
41121 Modena, Italy

Web: www.nano.cnr.it/index.php?mod=men&id=292

Q-SORT Science Bash: Beauty and Benefits of Nanobiology

[Peter Peters](#), a professor of Nanobiology at Maastricht University, gave an informative and highly entertaining presentation during a Science Bash entitled “Beauty and the Benefits of Nanobiology”. This event was held on May 29 2018 at the Schlosskapelle Gymnasium Zitadelle in Julich, and was attended by a group of high school students who had the chance to learn about the latest progress made in cryo electron microscopy from a leading expert in the field. For the students, it was also a great chance to talk

with working professionals about their career options in biology, physics and other science-related fields. A description of the talk can be found below.

Prof. Peter Peters during the Q-SORT Science Bash entitled “Beauty and the Benefits of Nanobiology”

About

Prof. Peter Peters was instrumental in improving cryo-immunogold electron microscopy (EM) and vitreous cryo-sectioning. His team discovered that mycobacteria causing tuberculosis move from the phagosome into the cytosol (one of the top 10 cited articles in tuberculosis in the last 10 years). He initiated the Netherlands Centre for Electron Nanoscopy (NeCEN). He co-directs the Maastricht Multimodal Molecular Imaging Institute, in which native unfixed cells are studied with 3D cryo-electron tomography in order to visualise molecular machines in the context of cellular organelles. His group aims to resolve the type VII secretion system of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* within the phagolysosome. He initiated a new start-up CryoSol-World, which will produce a next generation vitrification device called a Vitrojet. The Vitrojet, which was developed in Maastricht, has been distributed to more than 500 cryo-EM labs worldwide. His research has been reported in 120 articles with more than 25000 citations.

www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/m4i

Description

In the area of the life sciences, electron microscopy (EM) enables an in-depth understanding of the basic concept of life. EM is indispensable to address biological structures both at cellular and molecular scales. It has revealed how each cell of the human body is divided into membrane compartments with specialized functions that together organize a diversity of processes, such as protein synthesis, energy production, and distribution of genetic material. Recent developments in EM at extremely low temperatures even allow scientists to zoom in to atomic resolution and see individual proteins or protein complexes within the native environment of the cell. This provides critical insights in the molecular processes of diseases (e.g. transformation of cancer cells, disease-causing mechanisms in the ageing brain) and human development (e.g. differentiation and renewal of stem cells). Indeed, molecular and cellular defects underlie most diseases, and EM uniquely provides the resolution to study localization and structure of molecules such as proteins, together with the crucial structural information. EM applications are found in fundamental biological research, including infectiology (e.g., EM studies to understand how HIV infects a living

mammalian cell), neurobiology (identification of specific regions within the brain, followed by nanoscopic investigation with EM) and pathology (studying subtle pathologic phenotypes that are too small for light microscopy). Recent innovations in automated imaging in 2D (x,y axes; large-scale EM) and 3D (x,y,z axes; volume-EM) are creating unprecedented possibilities to reveal the architecture of cells within the context of their complex environment, such as tumors and even entire brains. On the molecular level, until recently, only X-ray crystallography and NMR spectroscopy were able to deliver the resolution necessary to describe the structure and understand the biological function of macromolecules at an atomic level. The limitation of crystallography, however, is that only systems that can be obtained at high yields and crystallized are accessible for this technique. The advent of a new generation of EMs, where samples are studied at cryogenic temperatures (cryo-EM), has revolutionized this field. Cryo-EM, selected the 'method of the year 2015' by Nature Methods, allows structural studies of biological systems without the need for crystallization. Not only has academic research been revolutionized by this, pharmaceutical and biotech industry have also embraced this emerging technology. For example, Genentech, Novartis, Pfizer and other companies have invested in their own top-end cryo-EM facilities. Cryo-EM opens a whole new avenue of biological research. Moreover, it covers a key resolution and spatial range window, that allows (bio)chemistry-driven research on molecular structure and biology-driven research on cellular structure to be bridged. For example, an atomic model of HIV-1 capsid-SP1 elucidated by cryo-EM reveals structures regulating assembly and maturation. These revolutions in the EM field have created worldwide excitement for EM, which is reflected in the numerous high-impact studies published in prestigious journals (e.g., over 200 papers in Nature, Cell and Science in the past 3 years).

Parallel worlds: From Electron Microscopes and Quantum Sorters

German version by Achim Raschka

Translated by David N. Winkler, Ph.D.

A few weeks ago, I received a message from a parallel universe – more precisely, I received, together with other Wikipedians in Cologne, an inquiry from Martin Rulsch on behalf of Lorenzo Losa, the President of Wikimedia Italia.

[Wikimedia Italia](#) was seeking help in the organization of an edit-a-thon at [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#).

Since Jülich was easy for me to reach and the topic of the edit-a-thon was scientific (of interest to me, because I am a biologist), I quickly volunteered my services.

The Q-SORT Wikipedia Edit-a-thon 2018 was organised by an EU-funded research project, Q-SORT. The project aims to develop novel techniques based on transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and quantum theory, and to further develop the TEM into a quantum sorter. As I imagine many of you are thinking, I was more than a little perplexed at this description. What is a quantum sorter? What do they want? What is this about?

I have given up trying to understand what the scientists are actually doing and have taken to focusing on my job: explaining to groups of students or assistants how Wikipedia works, how to edit and rearrange articles, etc.

I arrived in Jülich and discovered that this particular group did not comprise students but rather high-caliber scientists, including Rafal E. Dunin-Borkowski, head of the Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons; Giulio Pozzi, Professor at the University of Bologna; Marco Belleggia, Professor at the Danmarks Tekniske Universitet in Copenhagen, and other scientists who wanted to learn about improving Wikipedia with their expertise in electron microscopy and the physical fundamentals behind it.

Caption:Rafal E. Dunin-Borkowski, Director of the Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons

We had a very constructive afternoon and all of the participants were happy with the results of the work that was collectively carried out.

For example, an article about orbital angular momentum of free electrons and electron optics was created. Other scientists worked on articles or went over some articles and corrected mistakes. For nearly three hours, the group of 12 participants focused on the work, before it came to the end and our attention turned to a restaurant in Jülich, where good conversation and fresh asparagus were enjoyed.

Of course, in three hours you can hardly write or revise articles (one of the participants asked: “What to do if an article is completely bad – start from scratch?”) – but the project will last for four years and the revision of Wikipedia articles is an integral part of the agenda, which will be followed up at the next meetings and in the phases between them.

This must be done in order to make knowledge on the topic available to everyone and to incorporate new insights from the project into what is already known and freely available to the public.

Wikimedia Italia put it aptly in its blog post: “Il futuro della scienza passa attraverso Wikipedia” (“The future of science roams through Wikipedia”).

My personal conclusion: events of this kind can help advance Wikipedia in current research areas, and I would like to see more research projects picking up on this idea and advancing their fields. I am also willing to enter and learn about more parallel worlds.

The future of science comes through Wikipedia.

Italian version by Francesca Ussani, Communication Manager, Wikimedia Italia

Translated by David N. Winkler, Ph.D.

Can **complex scientific concepts** be communicated to the public through the pages of **Wikipedia**? According to team members of the **Q-SORT** project (A New Era in Electron Microscopy, financed by the

European Union), they not only can, but they must be. The free encyclopedia is an extremely efficient instrument for making the evidence and evolution of scientific research available to the widest possible audience.

“We work on frontier thematics related to the electron microscopy sector”, explained Vincenzo Grillo, researcher at CNR-NANO and Principal Investigator of Q-SORT, “and ours is one of the few projects financed by the European Union as part of the [FET-OPEN](#) programme that does not necessarily foresee an immediate industrial application: it has to do, rather, with fundamental research in an as-yet rather unexplored field. When we considered presenting to the general public the results of our work and advances in our field, we found a voice in the free encyclopedia.”

It was from this reflection that our [edit-a-thon](#) (a [writing event](#) on Wikipedia) was born – the first of three that will be organized during this project. The event took place on Sunday, May 27, 2018 in Germany at [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#) as part of the [International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time](#).

The event began with a training session, during which attendants learned the basic procedures and guidelines for contributing to the encyclopedia. Special attention was given to the creation, improvement, and translation of specific articles in English, beginning with academic literature made available by the organizers.

A page on [electron vortex beams](#) was created, while pages on [electron optics](#), [interaction-free measurements](#) and [bessel beams](#) were expanded. These articles needed to be updated or enriched with more references, which were added by the participants of the edit-a-thon.

“It is very important to us to make available on Wikipedia correct and complete information so that the greatest number of people that access the encyclopedia can discover our material”, Vincenzo explained, “in the same way as I do myself when, to avoid consulting academic papers, I open Wikipedia to quickly retrieve formulae or specific information.”

With the objective of making scientific knowledge ever more accessible, the Q-SORT team also decided **to provide open access to their academic publications**: a forward looking decision, considering that Wikipedia is among [the top ten access channels](#) to academic papers that are published on the internet.

For more information on the edit-a-thon, see the [project page on Wikipedia](#).

In the image: A scientist uses a transmission electron microscope. By CSIRO, CC BY 3.0, via Wikimedia Commons

Q-SORT and DIP projects held an international conference on electron beam shaping in Jülich (Germany)

On **May 28-30, 2018**, **Forschungszentrum Jülich** hosted the first **International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time**.

The event was organised jointly by partners of the projects **Quantum Sorter – A New Measurement Paradigm in Electron Microscopy (H2020-FETOPEN)** and **Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms (Deutsch-Israelische Projektkooperation grant)** with the support of **Forschungszentrum Jülich** and **Institute Nanoscience CNR (CNR-NANO)**.

The conference addressed challenges and opportunities in electron beam shaping and its applications. It showcased cutting-edge theoretical and experimental developments in the form of invited plenary talks and contributed presentations. Space was also devoted to product displays.

The event involved over eighty participants from all over the world and provided ample opportunity for networking and discussions. The participants had three very rewarding days, which were filled with interesting sessions, presentations, and posters.

The event was attended by scientists and researchers from leading institutions in the field of electron microscopy and quantum light optics, including CNR-NANO (Italy), Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany), the Technion (Israel), Tel-Aviv University (Israel), the Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light (Germany), the University of Glasgow (United Kingdom), the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (Italy), Maastricht University (The Netherlands), the University of Ottawa (Canada), Stanford University (USA), the University of Antwerp (Belgium), the University of Vienna (Austria), Uppsala University, Ulm University (Germany), the Paul Scherrer Institut (Switzerland), the University of Toronto (Canada), Tsinghua University (People's Republic of China), the University of York (United Kingdom), Delft University of Technology (The Netherlands), Friedrich-Alexander University (Germany), the University of St Andrews (United Kingdom), and the University of Göttingen (Germany). The private sector was represented by FEI – Thermo Fisher Scientific (The Netherlands – USA).

“It was an exciting and rewarding conference. I believe we were able to bring together the future of electron microscopy in the quantum régime. The conference speakers proposed ideas for future research tools and instruments, a true window into the future of the field”, said Vincenzo Grillo of the National Research Council in Italy. Dr. Grillo is the Scientific coordinator of Q-SORT and one of the organizers of the event, together with Rafal E. Dunin-Borkowski (Germany) and Ady Arie (Tel-Aviv University, Israel).

Program topics included the coherent manipulation of electron wavefunctions by the interaction of light and matter, inspired by recent progress in the use of light (quantum) optics to produce functional electron waveforms; studies of the foundational aspects of quantum physics and their applications to materials science; and ideas and methods for the near-interaction-free and dose-effective imaging of matter.

“It was refreshing to see forward-looking presentations about how electron microscopes can be used and developed in non-standard ways to understand fundamental concepts in physics and to link together scientific communities spanning the physical and life sciences”, explains Rafal Dunin-Borkowski.

Caption: Amir H. Tavabi (Forschungszentrum Jülich) carrying out a live demonstration from the electron microscope

Representatives from the creative industries were also in attendance.

Three outreach initiatives: a Q-SORT Wikipedia Edit-a-thon, three Q-SORT interdisciplinary webinars, and a Q-SORT Science Bash, were organised as part of the conference and were very well received.

QED, a partner of the Q-SORT consortium, produced the three webinars, which were webcast *via* Facebook Live.

They featured the conference invited speakers, Mark Kasevich (Stanford University, USA), Ido Kaminer (Technion, Israel), and John Veerbeek (University of Antwerp, Belgium).

Webinar views peaked at 8990 for the conference of Mark Kasevich (Stanford University, USA). Facebook posts related to the webinars reached over 60k people.

Peter Peters, Professor of Nano-Biology at Maastricht University, gave an informative and highly entertaining talk during the 'Science Bash', entitled "Beauty and the Benefits of Nanobiology". This event was held on May 29, 2018 at the Schlosskapelle of the Gymnasium Zitadelle in Julich, and was attended by high school students who had the chance to learn about the latest progress made in cryo electron microscopy from a leading expert in the field.

The Q-SORT 2018 Wikipedia Edit-a-thon was organised by QED in collaboration with Wikimedia Italia and Wikimedia Germany. The goal of this event was to edit and update Wikipedia articles on concepts related to the theme of the conference, including electron vortex beams, the double slit experiment with electrons, and synthetic holography, where information gaps currently exist. Scientists, researchers, and Ph.D. students participated in the research-and-writing event, which was a great occasion for everybody to get together and learn how Wikipedia works.

Further info: raffaella@qedproductions.co.uk

Download:

Book of Abstracts

Q-SORT Poster

Download the Q-SORT logo:

White – [eps./ai/pdf](#)

Black – [eps./ai/pdf](#)

International Conference on Electron Beam Shaping in Space and Time

Dates:

Monday 28 – Wednesday 30 May, 2018

Venue: Forschungszentrum Jülich, Germany

This conference is organized jointly by the partners of the projects Quantum Sorter – A new Measurement Paradigm in Electron Microscopy (H2020-FETOPEN)

Science and Applications of Electron Wavefunctions Shaped and Manipulated by Engineered Nanoholograms (Deutsch-Israelische Projektkooperation grant) with the support of Forschungszentrum Jülich.

Organisers:

Vincenzo Grillo (Modena, Italy)

Rafal Dunin-Borkowski (Jülich, Germany)

Ady Arie (Tel-Aviv, Israel)

Overview:

This conference aims to address challenges and opportunities in electron beam shaping and its applications. It will showcase cutting-edge theoretical and experimental developments in the form of invited plenary talks and contributed presentations and include space for product displays. There will be opportunities for networking and discussion, as well as an edit-a-thon, an interdisciplinary workshop and a webinar. Topics sought for the program include (but are not limited to):

- Coherent manipulation of electron wavefunctions by light interaction and matter, possibly inspired by recent progress in light (quantum) optics, to produce functional electron waveforms.
- Studies of the foundational aspects of quantum physics and their applications to materials science.
- Ideas and methods for near-interaction-free and dose-effective imaging of matter.

Invited speakers:

Johan Verbeeck

Benjamin McMorran

Ido Kaminer

Javier García de Abajo

Mark Kasevich

Claus Ropers

Peter Hommelhoff

Peter Kruit

Scientific motivation:

Electron beams are highly flexible and powerful probes of matter that can be shaped in both the spatial and the temporal domain. In addition to the traditional focusing of electron beams by electromagnetic lenses in electron microscopes, new technologies for electron beam shaping are being inspired by light optics, quantum optics and accelerator physics, including the use of nanofabricated holograms, novel photocathodes and alternative electron-optical configurations. In particular, frontier results in light optics offer some of the most promising new concepts for imaging with electrons.

New electron beam shapes include vortex beams, self-accelerating Airy beams and non diffracting Bessel beams. Electron beam shaping is being used to correct electron microscope lens aberrations, propose alternative contrast mechanisms, improve spatial resolution using super-oscillating wave functions, control electron spin and enable diffraction phase measurements. Innovative electron-optical configurations are also being developed for the measurement of electrons in different quantum bases (e.g., orbital angular momentum), thereby providing a form of highly efficient hardware compressed sensing, as well as opportunities for near-interaction-free imaging of electron-beam-sensitive materials.

Furthermore, light-electron interactions offer interesting approaches for shaping electron beams by means of the Kapitza-Dirac effect and accelerating them using laser-pumped nano-fabricated dielectric structures. Research is also being carried out into the production of coherent light using electrons (based on Smith-Purcell and transition radiation, Cherenkov processes and coherent Bremsstrahlung), while time-energy domain interference is being demonstrated using pump probe experiments.

1 – Edit-a-thon

Duration: 2:00 h

Location: Jülich (internet connection, 20 seats)

The goal of this event is to edit and update descriptions in Wikipedia of concepts such as electron vortex beams, two slit experiments with electrons and synthetic holography, where information gaps currently exist.

2 – Science bash

Duration: 1 Hour

Location: Maastricht?

This event will help the public to connect and engage with science. It will feature Prof. Peter Peters, who will speak about cryo electron microscopy. It will be free to anyone interested in attending.

3 – Interdisciplinary workshop and webinar

Duration: 1 hour

Location: Jülich

This will be the first in a series of interdisciplinary workshops and webinars aimed at promoting dialogue between the physics and biology/biochemistry communities. It will provide an opportunity for mutual learning mentored by senior scientists, in order to exchange ideas for furthering joint research and establishing a common language.

Submission guidelines:

3 page extended abstracts should be submitted online at [www....](#) (*using Jülich's website management system*).

Templates are available here:

docx Kit

LaTeX Kit

Contributions should be original and should not have been published or submitted elsewhere. They will be reviewed and selected by the scientific programme committee. They will have a **CCBYNCND** licence with open access, available shortly after the conference.

Please note that reviewing will be double blind. Therefore, please do not include authors' names and affiliations or references to websites and project names that would reveal authors' identities. Self-referencing should also be avoided. For instance, instead of "We previously showed (Brown, 2001)...", please use phrases such as "Brown (2001) previously showed ...". Each submitted contribution will be assessed by two reviewers.

Important dates:

- Submission of 3 page extended abstracts: 28 February 2018
- Response to authors: 16 March 2018
- Camera ready versions: 16 April 2018

Scientific programme committee:

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Registration:

The conference will be free of charge, but places are limited.

Coffee breaks, lunches and dinners will be provided.

Participants will be responsible for their own travel and hotel costs.

Please register and indicate your hotel preferences at [LINK] before May 21, 2018.

Dates: Monday 28 – Wednesday 30 May, 2018

Venue: [Forschungszentrum Jülich](#), Germany

Peter Peters on how knowledge of nanobiology can create happy, healthy sexual lives

Article originally featured on TEDx

When Peter Peters, is asked how he would describe himself in one sentence, he answers: “I am a passionate nanobiologist who aims to understand the inner working of healthy and diseased cells at the smallest detail in order to help combating diseases.” Quite a mouthful!

With his talk at TEDxMaastricht 2018, Peter revealed a secret on how to create ‘happy, healthy sexual lives’. “The awareness and understanding of the nanobiology of sperm and its pathogens will lead to higher acceptance of Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) vaccination and use of condoms in the emerging hookup culture creating safer sex. This will lead in lower incidence of cervical cancer (HPV), sexually transmitted diseases (STDs) that may lead to chronic illnesses (HIV) and infertility (Chlamydia).

Watch the talk here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bAcuNbJsuPY>

New ‘Quantum Sorter’ provides information on demand at the atomic scale

Radical techniques in electron microscopy could revolutionise studies in physics, biochemistry, materials and more.

For decades scientists, art-science aficionados and the wider public have marvelled at the beautiful worlds revealed by electron microscopy, from the hideous beauty of an insect's mouthparts to the shimmering world of meta-materials at the molecular level.

Microscopy is fundamental to unveil the smallest secrets of the natural world. Photo by Erop Камелевон Unsplash.

Modern machines can now fire powerful electron beams to produce images with single-atom resolution. But electron microscopes are much more than simple imagers. Probing properties like the composition of a sample or its magnetic properties, their flexibility as tools of investigation has made them precious allies for testing fundamental physics

But electron microscopy is not without problems for scientists to fix. One important issue is that electron beams can damage samples as they strike them. This so-called 'dose problem' is particularly serious when the sample is very delicate, like a protein for example. When imaging samples, the dose problem forces scientists to seek an awkward trade-off between resolution and sample integrity.

A new European project, [Q-SORT](#), is attempting to develop radically new techniques to explore and study fragile specimens at the microscopic level, uncovering an array of information that was previously hidden. Q-SORT exploits TEM (transmission electron microscopy), a technique in which a beam of electrons is passed through an ultra-thin slice of specimen to form an enlarged image.

Unlike previous incarnations of this technology, Q-SORT leverages the recently-acquired capacity to structure electron beams, turning the TEM into what project scientists call a 'quantum state sorter' or 'quantum sorter'. These sorters can probe the properties of samples with very few electrons, allowing scientists to answer tricky questions about the specimens with maximum efficiency and extremely low damage.

Cryomicroscopy is a branch of microscopy which can be used to better understand the structure of complex molecules such as proteins

This careful specimen handling is key in research fields like biology and biochemistry that typically feature delicate samples. In cryomicroscopy for example, a technique where a flash-frozen specimen is fed into an electron microscope, the techniques developed by Q-SORT can be used to recognise protein structures, symmetries and orientations. These proteins can be cell-signalling molecules, or parts of membranes, which ultimately provide us with knowledge of how cells and tissues function. Progress in the development of cryomicroscopy led to the Nobel Prize for Chemistry in 2017.

The new information gathered from quantum sorting could eventually be applicable in drug design for healthcare and next-generation biomedicine. What's more, the quantum sorter is a multipurpose tool which will be useful in many other fields besides biochemistry. For example, control of the information extracted by electrons from certain specimens could allow researchers to clarify many important physical mechanisms, such as those underpinning magnetic spin properties, or the physics of plasmons.

As project leader Vincenzo Grillo said: "We believe that the quantum sorter will become so important that it will eventually be part of every state-of-the-art TEM, since the new technology is easy to integrate with energy-loss spectrometry."

Q-SORT is funded by a €3 million grant by the European Commission's [Future and Emerging Technologies programme \(FET\)](#).

Photo by [Braden Collumon Unsplash](#)

This article was originally featured on FETX

Q-SORT to hold an International Conference in Erlangen

Q-SORT 2019 INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON QUANTUM IMAGING AND ELECTRON BEAM SHAPING

2-5 JULY 2019, Erlangen, Germany

This conference is organized jointly by the partners of the projects

Quantum Sorter – A new Measurement Paradigm in Electron Microscopy (H2020-FETOPEN) with the support of [Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light, Erlangen](#)

Recent developments in the spatial and temporal shaping of electron beams are on the verge of technological commercialisation, where they would provide routes towards image-resolution enhancement and novel microscopy techniques. Most of these methods, such as passive and dynamic wavepacket modulation, as well as structured light-matter interaction, are inspired by their optical counterpart and have now been explored in transmission electron microscopy. However, other schemes exist, inspired by quantum optics, such as so-called "interaction-free" methods, optimal quantum state tomography, and computational ghost imaging, which may be implemented in electron microscopy. All these new methods hold the promise of improving the imaging of dose-sensitive specimens.

The Q-SORT International Conference on Quantum Imaging and Electron Beam Shaping aims to gather experts from the fields of electron and laser beam shaping, free-space electron optics, and related sub-fields of quantum mechanics. Participants will present and share their latest discoveries and innovations. This meeting will be one of the first of its kind: it is thus uniquely positioned, since luminaries and pioneers from all the above research fields will be present. They will have the possibility to closely interact and exchange ideas for new, interdisciplinary collaborations.

Organisers:

Ady Arie, Tel Aviv University (Israel).

Rafal E. Dunin-Borkowski, Forschungszentrum Jülich (Germany)

Peter Hommelhoff, Friedrich–Alexander University Erlangen–Nürnberg, (Germany)

Ebrahim Karimi, University of Ottawa (Germany)

Gerd Leuchs, Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light, Germany

Vincenzo Grillo, CNR- NANO (Italy)

PRESS ROOM & DOWNLOADS (UPDATE!)

For all press/media needs please refer to the downloadable material below or email us at qsortpress@qedproductions.co.uk

Our team is here to respond to all media enquiries about Q-SORT.

There are many ways to stay current with our news and activities: you can sign up to our press mailing list, and/or read our professional blog and follow us on:

Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, Instagram.

To be included in the [press list](#), send us an email at qsortpress@qedproductions.co.uk with PRESS LIST YES as the subject.

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[Q-SORT Kick-off Meeting](#)

Download the [Outreach Toolkit](#)

[Q-SORT 2018 International Conference](#)

Download the [Outreach Toolkit](#)

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Q-SORT at a Glance

Title: Q-SORT. The Quantum Sorter: A New Measurement Paradigm in Electron Microscopy

Acronym: Q-SORT

Principal Investigator: Vincenzo Grillo

Tagline: Q-SORT. A New Era in Electron Microscopy

Start Date: 1 October 2017

End Date: 31 March 2021

Funding Body: European Commission
Research Executive Agency
Unit A5 - Fostering Novel Ideas: FET-Open

Project Partners:

CNR-NANO (Project scientific coordinator) - IT

The Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons - Forschungszentrum Jülich - DE

Maastricht University - NL
Thermo Fisher Scientific - NL
University of Glasgow - UK
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light - DE
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia - IT

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ANNEX 2: ABBREVIATIONS

SHORT NAME OF PARTICIPANTS

Partner	Country	Short Name
National Research Council (Project scientific coordinator)	Italy	CNR
Forschungszentrum Jülich, Ernst Ruska-Centre for Microscopy and Spectroscopy with Electrons	Germany	FZJ
FEI - Thermo Fisher Scientific	The Netherlands	FEI
The Max Planck Institute for the Science of Light	Germany	MPI
University of Glasgow, Department of Physics and Astronomy	United Kingdom	UG
QED Film & Stage Productions Ltd. - UK	United Kingdom	QED
University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Department of Physics, Informatics, and Mathematics - IT	Italy	UMR
Maastricht University, Maastricht MultiModal Molecular Imaging Institute	The Netherlands	MU

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Consortium Agreement	CA
Description of Action	DoA
Description of Work	DoW
European Commission	EC
Grant Agreement	GA
Kick-off Meeting	KoM
Project Management Board	PMB
Work Package	WP
Work Package Leader	WPL